

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Estrone

CHID: 22367 CASRN: 53-16-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J11

M4ID: 30006854

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00328 MAX_MED: 0.125 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Androstene-3,17-dione

CHID: 24523 CASRN: 63-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N10

M4ID: 30007528

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.082 MAX_MED: 0.0463 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethomorph

CHID: 34545 CASRN: 110488-70-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I22

M4ID: 30006867

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.168 MAX_MED: 0.202 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tebufenozide

CHID: 34948 CASRN: 112410-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C03

M4ID: 30007030

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0147 MAX_MED: -0.0845 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Testosterone propionate

CHID: 36515 CASRN: 57-85-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C07

M4ID: 30007410

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0128 MAX_MED: 0.0175 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: DMSO.POS (spid not in DB)

CHID: NA CASRN: NA

SPID(S): DMSO.POS

M4ID: 30007465

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00883 MAX_MED: 5.92e-08 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acetaminophen

CHID: 20006 CASRN: 103-90-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P21

M4ID: 30007084

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.092 MAX_MED: -0.0816 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acifluorfen

CHID: 20022 CASRN: 50594-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J03

M4ID: 30006862

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.238 MAX_MED: 0.295 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Allantoin

CHID: 20043 CASRN: 97-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P11

M4ID: 30007094

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.103 MAX_MED: -0.126 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Aminoanthraquinone
 CHID: 20068 CASRN: 117-79-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D15
 M4ID: 30007378

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0885 MAX_MED: 0.0262 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Amitrole

CHID: 20076 CASRN: 61-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078020

M4ID: 30007109

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0381 MAX_MED: 0.025 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: (E)-Anethole

CHID: 20087 CASRN: 4180-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D05

M4ID: 30007388

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.185 MAX_MED: 0.144 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Methoxyaniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20093 CASRN: 20265-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G07

M4ID: 30007314

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-31.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.122 MAX_MED: 0.0888 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Aspartame

CHID: 20107 CASRN: 22839-47-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K12

M4ID: 30006829

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0724 MAX_MED: -0.0681 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Aspirin

CHID: 20108 CASRN: 50-78-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D13

M4ID: 30007380

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0436 MAX_MED: 0.0376 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Atrazine

CHID: 20112 CASRN: 1912-24-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N11

M4ID: 30007527

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.031 MAX_MED: 0.0556 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium azide

CHID: 20121 CASRN: 26628-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D11

M4ID: 30006998

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.102 MAX_MED: 0.112 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Azobenzene

CHID: 20123 CASRN: 103-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C12

M4ID: 30007405

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.032 MAX_MED: -0.0702 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine

CHID: 20127 CASRN: 30516-87-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L14

M4ID: 30006803

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.291 MAX_MED: 0.24 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzidine

CHID: 20137 CASRN: 92-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G13

M4ID: 30007308

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.137 MAX_MED: 0.209 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium benzoate

CHID: 20140 CASRN: 532-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K11

M4ID: 30007214

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.344 MAX_MED: 0.357 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,3-Benzofuran

CHID: 20141 CASRN: 271-89-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D21

M4ID: 30006988

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-45.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.173 MAX_MED: 0.106 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzoic acid

CHID: 20143 CASRN: 65-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G12

M4ID: 30007309

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00954 MAX_MED: 0.0137 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2,3-Benzotriazole
 CHID: 20147 CASRN: 95-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N21
 M4ID: 30007132

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.27 MAX_MED: 0.187 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzyl acetate

CHID: 20151 CASRN: 140-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D23

M4ID: 30007370

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0415 MAX_MED: 0.0817 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Biphenyl

CHID: 20161 CASRN: 92-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I06

M4ID: 30007267

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.288 MAX_MED: 0.269 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol dibromide

CHID: 20164 CASRN: 3296-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I12

M4ID: 30007261

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0689 MAX_MED: 0.0924 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzyl butyl phthalate

CHID: 20205 CASRN: 85-68-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P16

M4ID: 30007474

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.117 MAX_MED: 0.0526 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylphenol

CHID: 20221 CASRN: 98-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B22

M4ID: 30007419

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0403 MAX_MED: -0.0176 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Caffeine

CHID: 20232 CASRN: 58-08-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K18

M4ID: 30007207

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.328 MAX_MED: 0.321 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Carbofuran

CHID: 20249 CASRN: 1563-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P06

M4ID: 30007099

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00439 MAX_MED: 0.0477 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Chloro-4-nitrobenzene

CHID: 20281 CASRN: 100-00-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B05

M4ID: 30007436

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-46.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.164 MAX_MED: 0.263 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloro-1,2-diaminobenzene

CHID: 20283 CASRN: 95-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M06

M4ID: 30006787

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.141 MAX_MED: 0.176 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Chloro-4-methylaniline

CHID: 20286 CASRN: 95-74-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F09

M4ID: 30007336

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00465 MAX_MED: 0.135 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Monuron

CHID: 20311 CASRN: 150-68-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J12

M4ID: 30007237

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-40.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.116 MAX_MED: 0.114 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Citric acid

CHID: 20332 CASRN: 77-92-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H23

M4ID: 30007274

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0399 MAX_MED: 0.117 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline

CHID: 20350 CASRN: 120-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E10

M4ID: 30006975

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0484 MAX_MED: -0.0619 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene
 CHID: 20409 CASRN: 53-70-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H04
 M4ID: 30007293

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0927 MAX_MED: 0.172 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propyzamide

CHID: 20420 CASRN: 23950-58-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K12

M4ID: 30007213

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.197 MAX_MED: 0.27 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dichlorobenzene
 CHID: 20431 CASRN: 106-46-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091014
 M4ID: 30007500

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	41.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.189 MAX_MED: 0.16 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dichlorprop

CHID: 20440 CASRN: 120-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B13

M4ID: 30007428

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0933 MAX_MED: 0.101 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-D Butyl ester

CHID: 20443 CASRN: 94-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H13

M4ID: 30007284

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.261 MAX_MED: 0.228 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol

CHID: 20462 CASRN: 111-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F18

M4ID: 30007327

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0161 MAX_MED: -0.0134 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethylaminoethanol
 CHID: 20505 CASRN: 108-01-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H24
 M4ID: 30006889

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.125 MAX_MED: 0.067 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylaniline

CHID: 20507 CASRN: 121-69-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E08

M4ID: 30007361

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.173 MAX_MED: -0.0999 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene

CHID: 20510 CASRN: 57-97-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E10

M4ID: 30007359

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.212 MAX_MED: 0.129 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,1-Dimethylhydrazine
 CHID: 20516 CASRN: 57-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H06
 M4ID: 30007291

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.23 MAX_MED: 0.188 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20528 CASRN: 606-20-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J06

M4ID: 30007243

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.249 MAX_MED: 0.246 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20529 CASRN: 121-14-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L02

M4ID: 30006815

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.349 MAX_MED: 0.259 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Endosulfan

CHID: 20560 CASRN: 115-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G03

M4ID: 30006934

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.359 MAX_MED: 0.355 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium erythorbate (1:1)

CHID: 20570 CASRN: 6381-77-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H14

M4ID: 30006899

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.115 MAX_MED: 0.242 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethylene glycol

CHID: 20597 CASRN: 107-21-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D22

M4ID: 30007371

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0728 MAX_MED: -0.0558 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Vinyl-1-cyclohexene dioxide

CHID: 20604 CASRN: 106-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078006

M4ID: 30007123

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.121 MAX_MED: 0.133 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 20605 CASRN: 104-76-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078021

M4ID: 30007108

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.195 MAX_MED: 0.295 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Finasteride

CHID: 20625 CASRN: 98319-26-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D22

M4ID: 30006987

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0785 MAX_MED: -0.0595 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluometuron

CHID: 20628 CASRN: 2164-17-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078012

M4ID: 30007117

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.032 MAX_MED: -0.00202 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5-Fluorouracil

CHID: 20634 CASRN: 51-21-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I02

M4ID: 30006887

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.245 MAX_MED: 0.208 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Glycerol

CHID: 20663 CASRN: 56-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C17

M4ID: 30007400

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.254 MAX_MED: 0.215 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Chloro-1,2-propanediol

CHID: 20664 CASRN: 96-24-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I09

M4ID: 30006880

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.123 MAX_MED: -0.0154 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Glycidol

CHID: 20666 CASRN: 556-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N20

M4ID: 30007133

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.186 MAX_MED: 0.245 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexachloro-1,3-butadiene

CHID: 20683 CASRN: 87-68-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I18

M4ID: 30007255

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.239 MAX_MED: 0.201 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane

CHID: 20685 CASRN: 319-85-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H10

M4ID: 30006903

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0812 MAX_MED: -0.02 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexachlorocyclopentadiene

CHID: 20688 CASRN: 77-47-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F06

M4ID: 30006955

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0978 MAX_MED: 0.0319 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methenamine

CHID: 20692 CASRN: 100-97-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G08

M4ID: 30006929

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0904 MAX_MED: 0.00264 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylhydrazine

CHID: 20710 CASRN: 122-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C15

M4ID: 30007018

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.144 MAX_MED: 0.11 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propham

CHID: 20766 CASRN: 122-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A10

M4ID: 30007455

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0245 MAX_MED: -0.0441 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: dL-Menthol

CHID: 20805 CASRN: 89-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I14

M4ID: 30007259

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.171 MAX_MED: 0.259 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
CHID: 20856 CASRN: 872-50-4
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A23
M4ID: 30007442

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.253 MAX_MED: 0.267 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 6-Methylquinoline

CHID: 20887 CASRN: 91-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C06

M4ID: 30007411

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00251 MAX_MED: 0.0139 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 6-Methyl-2-thiouracil
CHID: 20890 CASRN: 56-04-2
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F19
M4ID: 30007326

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.14 MAX_MED: 0.241 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Busulfan

CHID: 20910 CASRN: 55-98-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P15

M4ID: 30007475

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.279 MAX_MED: 0.0852 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Naphthalene

CHID: 20913 CASRN: 91-20-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M02

M4ID: 30006791

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.255 MAX_MED: 0.214 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Naphthaleneacetic acid

CHID: 20915 CASRN: 86-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F05

M4ID: 30006956

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.076 MAX_MED: 0.0809 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Naphthylamine

CHID: 20921 CASRN: 91-59-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G06

M4ID: 30007315

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-44.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.105 MAX_MED: 0.12 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nicotine

CHID: 20930 CASRN: 54-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D07

M4ID: 30007386

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-35.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00748 MAX_MED: 0.0869 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nicotinic acid

CHID: 20932 CASRN: 59-67-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J10

M4ID: 30007239

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.254 MAX_MED: 0.253 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Methyl-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20959 CASRN: 99-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G18

M4ID: 30006919

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.138 MAX_MED: 0.196 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nitrobenzene

CHID: 20964 CASRN: 98-95-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E23

M4ID: 30006962

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.234 MAX_MED: 0.156 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Nitrobenzoic acid
 CHID: 20966 CASRN: 62-23-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I03
 M4ID: 30006886

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.259 MAX_MED: 0.325 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nitrofen

CHID: 20970 CASRN: 1836-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N22

M4ID: 30007516

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.47 MAX_MED: 0.355 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodimethylamine

CHID: 21029 CASRN: 62-75-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P13

M4ID: 30007092

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0277 MAX_MED: 0.0112 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodipropylamine
 CHID: 21032 CASRN: 621-64-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J14
 M4ID: 30006851

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.319 MAX_MED: 0.312 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Oxazepam

CHID: 21087 CASRN: 604-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A15

M4ID: 30007450

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.143 MAX_MED: 0.125 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Oxydianiline

CHID: 21094 CASRN: 101-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G10

M4ID: 30007311

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0407 MAX_MED: 0.0645 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Oxytetracycline hydrochloride

CHID: 21097 CASRN: 2058-46-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P02

M4ID: 30007488

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.387 MAX_MED: 0.336 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phenothiazine

CHID: 21126 CASRN: 92-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D19

M4ID: 30007374

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.139 MAX_MED: 0.129 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenediamine

CHID: 21137 CASRN: 108-45-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A21

M4ID: 30007444

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.152 MAX_MED: 0.184 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Phenylphenol

CHID: 21151 CASRN: 90-43-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N03

M4ID: 30007535

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.156 MAX_MED: 0.262 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Picloram

CHID: 21160 CASRN: 1918-02-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K18

M4ID: 30006823

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.2 MAX_MED: 0.182 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Prednisone

CHID: 21185 CASRN: 53-03-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I05

M4ID: 30007268

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.33 MAX_MED: 0.324 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pebulate

CHID: 21199 CASRN: 1114-71-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H11

M4ID: 30007286

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-44.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.154 MAX_MED: 0.144 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propyl gallate

CHID: 21201 CASRN: 121-79-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B12

M4ID: 30007429

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.339 MAX_MED: 0.325 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 6-Propyl-2-thiouracil

CHID: 21209 CASRN: 51-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A20

M4ID: 30007445

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00431 MAX_MED: 0.0179 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium chlorite

CHID: 21272 CASRN: 7758-19-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J11

M4ID: 30007238

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.257 MAX_MED: 0.254 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2E,4E-Hexadienoic acid
 CHID: 21277 CASRN: 110-44-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K24
 M4ID: 30007201

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0918 MAX_MED: 0.109 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Disulfiram

CHID: 21322 CASRN: 97-77-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G21

M4ID: 30007300

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.357 MAX_MED: 0.299 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Thiabendazole

CHID: 21337 CASRN: 148-79-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A05

M4ID: 30007076

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.146 MAX_MED: 0.123 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Thiourea

CHID: 21348 CASRN: 62-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L17

M4ID: 30006800

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.312 MAX_MED: 0.268 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: dl-alpha-Tocopheryl acetate

CHID: 21356 CASRN: 52225-20-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D08

M4ID: 30007385

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0194 MAX_MED: 0.0422 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4,6-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 21386 CASRN: 88-06-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F06
 M4ID: 30007339

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.215 MAX_MED: 0.249 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Trifluralin

CHID: 21395 CASRN: 1582-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B08

M4ID: 30007049

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.133 MAX_MED: -0.117 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene

CHID: 21402 CASRN: 95-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I08

M4ID: 30006881

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0525 MAX_MED: 0.0431 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Urethane

CHID: 21427 CASRN: 51-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M11

M4ID: 30006782

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.202 MAX_MED: 0.208 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fumaric acid

CHID: 21518 CASRN: 110-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P23

M4ID: 30007082

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.13 MAX_MED: -0.0622 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21519 CASRN: 112-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N17

M4ID: 30007136

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.286 MAX_MED: 0.319 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Decanoic acid

CHID: 21554 CASRN: 334-48-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D21

M4ID: 30007372

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.117 MAX_MED: 0.152 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Heptanoic acid

CHID: 21600 CASRN: 111-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P03

M4ID: 30007487

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0714 MAX_MED: 0.0924 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexanoic acid

CHID: 21607 CASRN: 142-62-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N06

M4ID: 30007147

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.333 MAX_MED: 0.353 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octanal

CHID: 21643 CASRN: 124-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E18

M4ID: 30007351

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0498 MAX_MED: -0.0177 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octanoic acid

CHID: 21645 CASRN: 124-07-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P07

M4ID: 30007098

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.000509 MAX_MED: -0.0219 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid

CHID: 21666 CASRN: 544-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L23

M4ID: 30007178

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.191 MAX_MED: 0.283 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfoxide

CHID: 21735 CASRN: 67-68-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B11

M4ID: 30007046

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.114 MAX_MED: 0.159 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5,5-Dimethylhydantoin
 CHID: 21754 CASRN: 77-71-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J07
 M4ID: 30007242

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.223 MAX_MED: 0.288 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate

CHID: 21758 CASRN: 78-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078022

M4ID: 30007107

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.112 MAX_MED: 0.174 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-(2-Methylbutan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 21771 CASRN: 80-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A18

M4ID: 30007447

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.185 MAX_MED: 0.18 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Naphthol

CHID: 21793 CASRN: 90-15-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F01

M4ID: 30006960

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-35.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.217 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Quinoline

CHID: 21798 CASRN: 91-22-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I10

M4ID: 30006879

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0208 MAX_MED: 0.0472 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N-Diethylaniline

CHID: 21800 CASRN: 91-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N02

M4ID: 30007536

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.272 MAX_MED: 0.318 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: o-Cresol

CHID: 21808 CASRN: 95-48-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N23

M4ID: 30007130

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.119 MAX_MED: 0.09 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloroaniline
 CHID: 21815 CASRN: 95-76-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L22
 M4ID: 30006795

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.288 MAX_MED: 0.149 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Butanone oxime

CHID: 21821 CASRN: 96-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H21

M4ID: 30006892

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.373 MAX_MED: 0.256 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acetophenone

CHID: 21828 CASRN: 98-86-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H08

M4ID: 30007289

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-39.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.142 MAX_MED: 0.153 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N,4-Trimethylaniline

CHID: 21832 CASRN: 99-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078018

M4ID: 30007111

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.027 MAX_MED: -0.0754 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanone oxime
 CHID: 21842 CASRN: 100-64-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M10
 M4ID: 30006783

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.044 MAX_MED: 0.0263 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Ethyl-3-methylaniline

CHID: 21848 CASRN: 102-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N18

M4ID: 30007135

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.342 MAX_MED: 0.259 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethyl propanedioate

CHID: 21863 CASRN: 105-53-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F20

M4ID: 30006941

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0422 MAX_MED: 0.0225 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 21864 CASRN: 105-67-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M08

M4ID: 30006785

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0029 MAX_MED: 0.0457 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: p-Cresol

CHID: 21869 CASRN: 106-44-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A07

M4ID: 30007458

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-26.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.181 MAX_MED: 0.222 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Methyl-2,4-pentanedio1

CHID: 21885 CASRN: 107-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H07

M4ID: 30007290

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-31.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.19 MAX_MED: 0.179 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Pentanone

CHID: 21888 CASRN: 107-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P12

M4ID: 30007478

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0983 MAX_MED: -0.148 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanol

CHID: 21894 CASRN: 108-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F17

M4ID: 30007328

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-64.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0608 MAX_MED: 0.0598 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propanedinitrile

CHID: 21907 CASRN: 109-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F19

M4ID: 30006942

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.219 MAX_MED: 0.244 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(Ethylamino)ethanol
 CHID: 21922 CASRN: 110-73-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G04
 M4ID: 30007317

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0165 MAX_MED: 0.00996 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethylene glycol monoethyl ether acetate

CHID: 21928 CASRN: 111-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J20

M4ID: 30007229

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.2 MAX_MED: 0.189 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Octanol

CHID: 21940 CASRN: 111-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F21

M4ID: 30007324

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00916 MAX_MED: 0.0283 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21941 CASRN: 111-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G18

M4ID: 30007303

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-39.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.138 MAX_MED: 0.0812 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Decanol

CHID: 21946 CASRN: 112-30-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I22

M4ID: 30007251

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0481 MAX_MED: 0.0889 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phenyl salicylate

CHID: 21957 CASRN: 118-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L19

M4ID: 30007182

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.257 MAX_MED: 0.319 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzophenone

CHID: 21961 CASRN: 119-61-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D18

M4ID: 30007375

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0605 MAX_MED: 0.0716 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 21969 CASRN: 121-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M24

M4ID: 30007153

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0847 MAX_MED: 0.113 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diphenylamine

CHID: 21975 CASRN: 122-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J18

M4ID: 30007231

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-42.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.135 MAX_MED: 0.157 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Phenoxyethanol

CHID: 21976 CASRN: 122-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C22

M4ID: 30007395

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.114 MAX_MED: -0.114 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethanolamine

CHID: 22000 CASRN: 141-43-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H21

M4ID: 30007276

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.128 MAX_MED: 0.202 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Nonanol

CHID: 22008 CASRN: 143-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M22

M4ID: 30007155

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.168 MAX_MED: 0.19 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Disulfoton

CHID: 22018 CASRN: 298-04-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B23

M4ID: 30007034

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00515 MAX_MED: 0.000325 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bromacil

CHID: 22020 CASRN: 314-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G10

M4ID: 30006927

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0426 MAX_MED: 0.0425 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Flavone

CHID: 22048 CASRN: 525-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G11

M4ID: 30006926

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.128 MAX_MED: 0.163 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dichlorobenzene
 CHID: 22056 CASRN: 541-73-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C22
 M4ID: 30007011

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00408 MAX_MED: -0.0254 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: gamma-Decanolactone
 CHID: 22109 CASRN: 706-14-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D17
 M4ID: 30007376

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-40.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.103 MAX_MED: 0.119 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propanil

CHID: 22111 CASRN: 709-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N24

M4ID: 30007514

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.36 MAX_MED: 0.352 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloro-1-butene
 CHID: 22113 CASRN: 760-23-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H24
 M4ID: 30007273

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0175 MAX_MED: 0.00942 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: (Z)-3-Hexen-1-ol

CHID: 22137 CASRN: 928-96-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M18

M4ID: 30007159

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.268 MAX_MED: 0.307 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: EPN

CHID: 22174 CASRN: 2104-64-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078010

M4ID: 30007119

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0151 MAX_MED: -0.0262 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,3,6-Trimethylphenol

CHID: 22187 CASRN: 2416-94-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G11

M4ID: 30007310

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-47.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.182 MAX_MED: 0.214 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Resmethrin

CHID: 22253 CASRN: 10453-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H03

M4ID: 30006910

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.124 MAX_MED: 0.144 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triphenylethylene

CHID: 22320 CASRN: 58-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K06

M4ID: 30006835

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.145 MAX_MED: 0.277 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Vinclozolin

CHID: 22361 CASRN: 50471-44-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F22

M4ID: 30006939

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.183 MAX_MED: 0.282 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5 α -Dihydrotestosterone

CHID: 22364 CASRN: 521-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C11

M4ID: 30007022

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.028 MAX_MED: 0.114 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 17alpha-Estradiol

CHID: 22377 CASRN: 57-91-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K06

M4ID: 30007219

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.255 MAX_MED: 0.223 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Methylenebis(2,6-di-t-butylphenol)

CHID: 22411 CASRN: 118-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I02

M4ID: 30007271

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0027 MAX_MED: 0.0216 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Melatonin

CHID: 22421 CASRN: 73-31-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E07

M4ID: 30007362

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00139 MAX_MED: 0.037 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Diaminobiphenyl methane

CHID: 22422 CASRN: 101-77-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P18

M4ID: 30007087

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.153 MAX_MED: -0.178 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phenolphthalin

CHID: 22439 CASRN: 81-90-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N05

M4ID: 30007533

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.266 MAX_MED: 0.341 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butylbenzene

CHID: 22472 CASRN: 104-51-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C21

M4ID: 30007012

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.249 MAX_MED: 0.237 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Corticosterone

CHID: 22474 CASRN: 50-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091005

M4ID: 30007509

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.228 MAX_MED: 0.131 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: E-Cinnamic acid

CHID: 22489 CASRN: 140-10-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B01

M4ID: 30007440

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0633 MAX_MED: 0.044 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Letrozole

CHID: 23202 CASRN: 112809-51-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K22

M4ID: 30006819

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.246 MAX_MED: 0.164 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Mifepristone

CHID: 23322 CASRN: 84371-65-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B01

M4ID: 30007056

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.113 MAX_MED: 0.112 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyridoxine

CHID: 23541 CASRN: 65-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G01

M4ID: 30006936

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.281 MAX_MED: 0.263 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Retinol

CHID: 23556 CASRN: 68-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H14

M4ID: 30007283

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0721 MAX_MED: 0.136 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butanedioic acid

CHID: 23602 CASRN: 110-15-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I07

M4ID: 30006882

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.187 MAX_MED: 0.185 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 6-Thioguanine

CHID: 23652 CASRN: 154-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E05

M4ID: 30007364

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0751 MAX_MED: 0.139 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Warfarin

CHID: 23742 CASRN: 81-81-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B07

M4ID: 30007434

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0395 MAX_MED: 0.105 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: D-Xylose

CHID: 23745 CASRN: 58-86-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J12

M4ID: 30006853

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.077 MAX_MED: 0.0477 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 23792 CASRN: 99-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D06

M4ID: 30007387

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0318 MAX_MED: 0.0291 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isophorone diisocyanate

CHID: 23826 CASRN: 4098-71-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B08

M4ID: 30007433

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0682 MAX_MED: 0.0601 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Polydimethylsiloxane

CHID: 23833 CASRN: 9016-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A12

M4ID: 30007069

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0997 MAX_MED: -0.0226 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acenaphthylene

CHID: 23845 CASRN: 208-96-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A06

M4ID: 30007459

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.045 MAX_MED: 0.0151 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acephate

CHID: 23846 CASRN: 30560-19-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C19

M4ID: 30007398

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.183 MAX_MED: 0.206 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acetochlor

CHID: 23848 CASRN: 34256-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E24

M4ID: 30006961

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.234 MAX_MED: 0.146 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Amitraz

CHID: 23871 CASRN: 33089-61-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D08

M4ID: 30007001

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0508 MAX_MED: 0.0275 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Anisidine

CHID: 23877 CASRN: 90-04-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I10

M4ID: 30007263

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-41.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0827 MAX_MED: 0.0983 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Clofentezine

CHID: 23881 CASRN: 74115-24-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M05

M4ID: 30006788

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.293 MAX_MED: 0.178 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Asulam

CHID: 23890 CASRN: 3337-71-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F10

M4ID: 30007335

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0581 MAX_MED: -0.0964 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benfluralin

CHID: 23899 CASRN: 1861-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L04

M4ID: 30006813

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0639 MAX_MED: -0.0224 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bentazone

CHID: 23901 CASRN: 25057-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F04

M4ID: 30006957

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.126 MAX_MED: -0.0714 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butylate

CHID: 23936 CASRN: 2008-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B05

M4ID: 30007052

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-26.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0703 MAX_MED: 0.143 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Carbosulfan

CHID: 23950 CASRN: 55285-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A15

M4ID: 30007066

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.112 MAX_MED: 0.11 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexylamine

CHID: 23996 CASRN: 108-91-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F08

M4ID: 30007337

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0201 MAX_MED: 0.00166 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyromazine

CHID: 23999 CASRN: 66215-27-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091007

M4ID: 30007507

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.226 MAX_MED: 0.241 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethyl sulfate

CHID: 24045 CASRN: 64-67-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M20

M4ID: 30007157

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.137 MAX_MED: 0.217 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfate

CHID: 24055 CASRN: 77-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D03

M4ID: 30007006

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0675 MAX_MED: 0.0274 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethylamine

CHID: 24057 CASRN: 124-40-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J05

M4ID: 30006860

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.217 MAX_MED: 0.276 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine
 CHID: 24059 CASRN: 119-93-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G09
 M4ID: 30006928

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.249 MAX_MED: 0.193 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24062 CASRN: 95-65-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E15

M4ID: 30006970

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.225 MAX_MED: 0.209 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24063 CASRN: 576-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A19

M4ID: 30007446

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.111 MAX_MED: 0.125 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diphenamid

CHID: 24072 CASRN: 957-51-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B12

M4ID: 30007045

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.044 MAX_MED: 0.0717 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethion

CHID: 24086 CASRN: 563-12-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E19

M4ID: 30007350

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0629 MAX_MED: 0.111 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Butoxyethanol

CHID: 24097 CASRN: 111-76-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M12

M4ID: 30007165

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.153 MAX_MED: 0.168 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fenamiphos

CHID: 24102 CASRN: 22224-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C08

M4ID: 30007025

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00998 MAX_MED: -0.00999 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Flutolanil

CHID: 24109 CASRN: 66332-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G17

M4ID: 30006920

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.146 MAX_MED: 0.286 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isopropalin

CHID: 24157 CASRN: 33820-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N12

M4ID: 30007141

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-26.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.226 MAX_MED: 0.173 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methacrylonitrile

CHID: 24176 CASRN: 126-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C20

M4ID: 30007013

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.107 MAX_MED: -0.128 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Mecoprop

CHID: 24194 CASRN: 93-65-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P03

M4ID: 30007102

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.141 MAX_MED: -0.0377 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: m-Cresol

CHID: 24200 CASRN: 108-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I19

M4ID: 30006870

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.412 MAX_MED: 0.365 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Molinate

CHID: 24206 CASRN: 2212-67-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I13

M4ID: 30007260

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.225 MAX_MED: 0.208 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nitrapyrin

CHID: 24216 CASRN: 1929-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G04

M4ID: 30006933

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.064 MAX_MED: 0.0623 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Oxyfluorfen

CHID: 24241 CASRN: 42874-03-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L08

M4ID: 30006809

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.223 MAX_MED: 0.212 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pendimethalin

CHID: 24245 CASRN: 40487-42-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P20

M4ID: 30007470

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.263 MAX_MED: 0.325 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phosphoric acid

CHID: 24263 CASRN: 7664-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K14

M4ID: 30006827

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.254 MAX_MED: 0.22 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Prometryn

CHID: 24272 CASRN: 7287-19-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G16

M4ID: 30006921

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0952 MAX_MED: 0.105 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexythiazox

CHID: 24299 CASRN: 78587-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I24

M4ID: 30006865

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.19 MAX_MED: 0.173 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sethoxydim

CHID: 24304 CASRN: 74051-80-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D09

M4ID: 30007000

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0691 MAX_MED: 0.0412 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium fluoroacetate
 CHID: 24311 CASRN: 62-74-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N13
 M4ID: 30007140

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.182 MAX_MED: 0.196 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Myclobutanil

CHID: 24315 CASRN: 88671-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G24

M4ID: 30007297

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.0996 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tebuthiuron

CHID: 24316 CASRN: 34014-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M04

M4ID: 30006789

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0192 MAX_MED: 0.0389 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2,4,5-Tetrachlorobenzene

CHID: 24320 CASRN: 95-94-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C24

M4ID: 30007009

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.138 MAX_MED: -0.156 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Thiophanate-methyl

CHID: 24338 CASRN: 23564-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I19

M4ID: 30007254

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.257 MAX_MED: 0.335 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 24368 CASRN: 112-50-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J02

M4ID: 30006863

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.235 MAX_MED: 0.227 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acetic acid

CHID: 24394 CASRN: 64-19-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078023

M4ID: 30007106

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.359 MAX_MED: 0.314 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Aminobenzoic acid
 CHID: 24466 CASRN: 150-13-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C13
 M4ID: 30007404

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0997 MAX_MED: 0.119 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzyl salicylate

CHID: 24598 CASRN: 118-58-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F07

M4ID: 30007338

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0578 MAX_MED: 0.0543 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 24621 CASRN: 111-96-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G03

M4ID: 30007318

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.233 MAX_MED: 0.261 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-propanol

CHID: 24657 CASRN: 627-18-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E05

M4ID: 30006980

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.199 MAX_MED: 0.115 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butanal oxime

CHID: 24664 CASRN: 110-69-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A12

M4ID: 30007453

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.045 MAX_MED: -0.0548 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylamine

CHID: 24681 CASRN: 75-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P18

M4ID: 30007472

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.128 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butyl glycidyl ether

CHID: 24691 CASRN: 2426-08-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B09

M4ID: 30007048

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0605 MAX_MED: 0.115 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: D-Camphor

CHID: 24721 CASRN: 464-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G14

M4ID: 30007307

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0477 MAX_MED: 0.0305 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Diaminotoluene

CHID: 24930 CASRN: 496-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M03

M4ID: 30006790

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.322 MAX_MED: 0.271 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Di-tert-butyl peroxide
 CHID: 24955 CASRN: 110-05-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F23
 M4ID: 30006938

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.135 MAX_MED: 0.156 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Dichlorodiphenyl sulfone

CHID: 24986 CASRN: 80-07-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B22

M4ID: 30007035

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.195 MAX_MED: 0.178 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Troclosesene

CHID: 24993 CASRN: 2782-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A19

M4ID: 30007062

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0758 MAX_MED: 0.0508 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzal chloride

CHID: 25014 CASRN: 98-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D05

M4ID: 30007004

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00707 MAX_MED: 0.0183 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 25049 CASRN: 111-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I24

M4ID: 30007249

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0325 MAX_MED: 0.11 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethylenetriamine

CHID: 25050 CASRN: 111-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N03

M4ID: 30007150

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.239 MAX_MED: 0.351 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dihexyl phthalate

CHID: 25068 CASRN: 84-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H12

M4ID: 30007285

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.101 MAX_MED: 0.0926 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diisobutyl ketone

CHID: 25080 CASRN: 108-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D12

M4ID: 30007381

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0092 MAX_MED: 0.011 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl adipate

CHID: 25096 CASRN: 627-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K16

M4ID: 30007209

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0655 MAX_MED: 0.197 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl glutarate

CHID: 25122 CASRN: 1119-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J22

M4ID: 30007227

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0524 MAX_MED: 0.0788 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dimethylolurea

CHID: 25141 CASRN: 140-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M12

M4ID: 30006781

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0896 MAX_MED: -0.0762 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Divinylbenzene

CHID: 25216 CASRN: 1321-74-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K04

M4ID: 30007221

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.112 MAX_MED: 0.209 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: (2-Dodecenyl)succinic anhydride

CHID: 25217 CASRN: 19780-11-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J02

M4ID: 30007247

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.17 MAX_MED: 0.12 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexanoic acid

CHID: 25293 CASRN: 149-57-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L12

M4ID: 30007189

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.222 MAX_MED: 0.211 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate

CHID: 25300 CASRN: 1241-94-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G17

M4ID: 30007304

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.324 MAX_MED: 0.28 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5-Ethylidene-2-norbornene

CHID: 25306 CASRN: 16219-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H22

M4ID: 30006891

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.329 MAX_MED: 0.36 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Formamide

CHID: 25337 CASRN: 75-12-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K20

M4ID: 30007205

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.186 MAX_MED: 0.213 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexamethyldisilazane
 CHID: 25395 CASRN: 999-97-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N23
 M4ID: 30007515

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	44.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.499 MAX_MED: 0.356 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxy-2-methylpropanenitrile

CHID: 25427 CASRN: 75-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G20

M4ID: 30006917

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.132 MAX_MED: 0.175 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 6-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl disulfide

CHID: 25429 CASRN: 6088-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D13

M4ID: 30006996

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0566 MAX_MED: 0.0466 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hydroxyurea

CHID: 25438 CASRN: 127-07-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F24

M4ID: 30006937

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0253 MAX_MED: -0.0789 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isopentyl alcohol

CHID: 25469 CASRN: 123-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N19

M4ID: 30007134

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.184 MAX_MED: 0.256 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl acetate

CHID: 25478 CASRN: 108-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P20

M4ID: 30007085

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0915 MAX_MED: -0.0656 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Linalool

CHID: 25502 CASRN: 78-70-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G23

M4ID: 30007298

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.299 MAX_MED: 0.3 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Linoleic acid

CHID: 25505 CASRN: 60-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C08

M4ID: 30007409

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0157 MAX_MED: 0.0647 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Maltol

CHID: 25523 CASRN: 118-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B21

M4ID: 30007420

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-35.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0485 MAX_MED: 0.116 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl 2-aminobenzoate
 CHID: 25567 CASRN: 134-20-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H04
 M4ID: 30006909

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0939 MAX_MED: -0.118 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Myrcene

CHID: 25692 CASRN: 123-35-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E16

M4ID: 30006969

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0808 MAX_MED: -0.0808 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Ethoxyaniline

CHID: 25864 CASRN: 156-43-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A09

M4ID: 30007072

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.155 MAX_MED: 0.185 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethyl 3-phenylglycidate

CHID: 25886 CASRN: 121-39-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D01

M4ID: 30007392

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0999 MAX_MED: 0.15 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Terephthalic acid

CHID: 26080 CASRN: 100-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B14

M4ID: 30007427

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0146 MAX_MED: 0.0334 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride

CHID: 26102 CASRN: 117-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I03

M4ID: 30007270

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.404 MAX_MED: 0.325 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tolyltriazole

CHID: 26171 CASRN: 29385-43-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N11

M4ID: 30007142

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-31.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.163 MAX_MED: 0.178 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Trimellitic anhydride
 CHID: 26235 CASRN: 552-30-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G16
 M4ID: 30007305

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.185 MAX_MED: -0.0683 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triphenyl phosphite
 CHID: 26252 CASRN: 101-02-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H17
 M4ID: 30006896

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.255 MAX_MED: 0.301 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Camphene

CHID: 26488 CASRN: 79-92-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C23

M4ID: 30007394

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.216 MAX_MED: 0.193 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide

CHID: 26513 CASRN: 85-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M16

M4ID: 30007161

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0631 MAX_MED: 0.124 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Symclosene

CHID: 26523 CASRN: 87-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I04

M4ID: 30006885

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0236 MAX_MED: -0.0266 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Tert-Butyl-5-methylphenol

CHID: 26529 CASRN: 88-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C05

M4ID: 30007028

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.32 MAX_MED: 0.301 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol bis(2-ethylhexanoate)

CHID: 26564 CASRN: 94-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F03

M4ID: 30006958

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00779 MAX_MED: 0.0676 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylcyclohexanol

CHID: 26623 CASRN: 98-52-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B13

M4ID: 30007044

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.138 MAX_MED: 0.153 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Diisopropylbenzene

CHID: 26640 CASRN: 99-62-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P19

M4ID: 30007086

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0367 MAX_MED: -0.0694 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenedicarbonyl dichloride

CHID: 26641 CASRN: 99-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P07

M4ID: 30007483

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0256 MAX_MED: -0.0385 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: p-Cymene

CHID: 26645 CASRN: 99-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L09

M4ID: 30006808

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0372 MAX_MED: 0.0735 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid

CHID: 26647 CASRN: 99-96-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L14

M4ID: 30007187

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.262 MAX_MED: 0.295 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)octanal

CHID: 26684 CASRN: 101-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J16

M4ID: 30007233

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0963 MAX_MED: 0.0231 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triacetin

CHID: 26691 CASRN: 102-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K22

M4ID: 30007203

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0789 MAX_MED: 0.153 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl acetate

CHID: 26694 CASRN: 103-09-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D03

M4ID: 30007390

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00948 MAX_MED: -0.0133 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: (2Z)-3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-ol

CHID: 26728 CASRN: 106-25-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B18

M4ID: 30007423

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0595 MAX_MED: 0.0088 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-pentanol
 CHID: 26781 CASRN: 108-11-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H19
 M4ID: 30007278

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.13 MAX_MED: 0.164 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Methylaniline

CHID: 26792 CASRN: 108-44-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L18

M4ID: 30007183

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.284 MAX_MED: 0.345 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzenethiol

CHID: 26811 CASRN: 108-98-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M04

M4ID: 30007173

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0904 MAX_MED: 0.153 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl tetradecanoate

CHID: 26838 CASRN: 110-27-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B06

M4ID: 30007435

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-56.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0966 MAX_MED: 0.0962 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl decanoate

CHID: 26842 CASRN: 110-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P21

M4ID: 30007469

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.24 MAX_MED: 0.204 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl octanoate

CHID: 26864 CASRN: 111-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J21

M4ID: 30006844

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.375 MAX_MED: 0.291 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Ethanedio1 diacetate

CHID: 26880 CASRN: 111-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N18

M4ID: 30007520

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.354 MAX_MED: 0.323 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 26912 CASRN: 112-35-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H17

M4ID: 30007280

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.282 MAX_MED: 0.222 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tetraethylene glycol
 CHID: 26922 CASRN: 112-60-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E17
 M4ID: 30007352

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.183 MAX_MED: 0.197 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol

CHID: 26943 CASRN: 115-77-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M13

M4ID: 30007164

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.266 MAX_MED: 0.274 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 26997 CASRN: 123-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B23

M4ID: 30007418

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0342 MAX_MED: 0.0673 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate

CHID: 27050 CASRN: 128-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P10

M4ID: 30007095

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0577 MAX_MED: -0.109 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Naphthalenol

CHID: 27061 CASRN: 135-19-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K10

M4ID: 30007215

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.208 MAX_MED: 0.215 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium phenolate

CHID: 27072 CASRN: 139-02-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F07

M4ID: 30006954

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.021 MAX_MED: 0.0619 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bis(2-ethylhexyl) maleate

CHID: 27094 CASRN: 142-16-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L03

M4ID: 30007198

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.283 MAX_MED: 0.278 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1H-1,2,4-Triazole

CHID: 27131 CASRN: 288-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078015

M4ID: 30007114

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.248 MAX_MED: 0.229 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Cyclopentadiene
 CHID: 27191 CASRN: 542-92-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J20
 M4ID: 30006845

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.322 MAX_MED: 0.341 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Methylphthalimide
 CHID: 27198 CASRN: 550-44-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P08
 M4ID: 30007097

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0272 MAX_MED: -0.0302 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl isothiocyanate
 CHID: 27204 CASRN: 556-61-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G24
 M4ID: 30006913

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.141 MAX_MED: 0.187 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane

CHID: 27205 CASRN: 556-67-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G14

M4ID: 30006923

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.258 MAX_MED: 0.281 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Pyrrolidinone

CHID: 27246 CASRN: 616-45-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H19

M4ID: 30006894

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.273 MAX_MED: 0.312 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl formate

CHID: 27258 CASRN: 625-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F03

M4ID: 30007342

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0599 MAX_MED: 0.0671 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pentyl acetate

CHID: 27263 CASRN: 628-63-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J23

M4ID: 30007226

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0788 MAX_MED: 0.129 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Phenoxy-2-propanol
 CHID: 27312 CASRN: 770-35-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H20
 M4ID: 30006893

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.144 MAX_MED: 0.178 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diisooctyl adipate

CHID: 27388 CASRN: 1330-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A13

M4ID: 30007452

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0548 MAX_MED: 0.0847 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phenolsulfonic acid

CHID: 27390 CASRN: 1333-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B07

M4ID: 30007050

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0682 MAX_MED: 0.144 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-D sodium salt

CHID: 27496 CASRN: 2702-72-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H18

M4ID: 30007279

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.177 MAX_MED: 0.196 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Potassium 2-ethylhexanoate

CHID: 27525 CASRN: 3164-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G19

M4ID: 30006918

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.246 MAX_MED: 0.316 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Butylbenzenesulfonamide

CHID: 27540 CASRN: 3622-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H09

M4ID: 30006904

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0796 MAX_MED: 0.068 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Chlorobenzotrithloride

CHID: 27593 CASRN: 5216-25-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P01

M4ID: 30007489

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.106 MAX_MED: 0.129 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Malic acid

CHID: 27640 CASRN: 6915-15-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P12

M4ID: 30007093

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.107 MAX_MED: -0.131 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzenemethanol

CHID: 27756 CASRN: 13826-35-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L22

M4ID: 30007179

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0127 MAX_MED: 0.168 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid

CHID: 27770 CASRN: 15214-89-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L18

M4ID: 30006799

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.224 MAX_MED: 0.303 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl monooleate

CHID: 27875 CASRN: 25496-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P22

M4ID: 30007468

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.139 MAX_MED: 0.0032 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ammonium xylene sulfonate

CHID: 27899 CASRN: 26447-10-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C04

M4ID: 30007413

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0493 MAX_MED: -0.0441 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Neodecanoic acid

CHID: 27916 CASRN: 26896-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H07

M4ID: 30006906

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0879 MAX_MED: 0.0785 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diisodecyl hexanedioate

CHID: 27924 CASRN: 27178-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B24

M4ID: 30007033

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.026 MAX_MED: -0.0513 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 27983 CASRN: 34590-94-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F23

M4ID: 30007322

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0289 MAX_MED: -0.00039 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Hexadecanol

CHID: 27991 CASRN: 36653-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H08

M4ID: 30006905

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.158 MAX_MED: -0.158 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dichlormid

CHID: 27997 CASRN: 37764-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D11

M4ID: 30007382

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-35.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0463 MAX_MED: 0.0275 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: DINP branched

CHID: 28665 CASRN: 68515-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H03

M4ID: 30007294

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.233 MAX_MED: 0.233 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3,7-Dimethyl-3-octanol

CHID: 29110 CASRN: 78-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F13

M4ID: 30007332

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0791 MAX_MED: 0.14 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol

CHID: 29128 CASRN: 97-99-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078004

M4ID: 30007125

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0812 MAX_MED: 0.0206 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyclopentanone

CHID: 29154 CASRN: 120-92-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I04

M4ID: 30007269

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.113 MAX_MED: 0.145 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)-heptanal

CHID: 29157 CASRN: 122-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J24

M4ID: 30007225

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0238 MAX_MED: 0.0676 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,6,8-Trimethyl-4-nonanol

CHID: 29159 CASRN: 123-17-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J15

M4ID: 30007234

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.248 MAX_MED: 0.3 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 29162 CASRN: 126-06-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E07

M4ID: 30006978

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.179 MAX_MED: 0.137 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one

CHID: 29170 CASRN: 141-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A03

M4ID: 30007462

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-31.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.198 MAX_MED: 0.16 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methylionone

CHID: 29214 CASRN: 1335-46-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P17

M4ID: 30007088

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0939 MAX_MED: -0.112 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Clopyralid

CHID: 29221 CASRN: 1702-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D04

M4ID: 30007005

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.155 MAX_MED: -0.0806 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tripropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 29329 CASRN: 25498-49-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K04

M4ID: 30006837

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0252 MAX_MED: -0.0555 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acetyl cedrene

CHID: 29353 CASRN: 32388-55-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B17

M4ID: 30007424

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-42.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0325 MAX_MED: 0.0472 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diazolidinyl urea

CHID: 29559 CASRN: 78491-02-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J18

M4ID: 30006847

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.172 MAX_MED: 0.161 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methacrylamide

CHID: 29600 CASRN: 79-39-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J19

M4ID: 30007230

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.273 MAX_MED: 0.294 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Limonene

CHID: 29612 CASRN: 138-86-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I23

M4ID: 30007250

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.279 MAX_MED: 0.266 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Thiocyanic acid, ammonium salt

CHID: 29653 CASRN: 1762-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M24

M4ID: 30007538

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.336 MAX_MED: 0.361 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 29661 CASRN: 3452-97-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C23

M4ID: 30007010

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.115 MAX_MED: 0.238 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Silica

CHID: 29677 CASRN: 7631-86-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J17

M4ID: 30007232

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.316 MAX_MED: 0.302 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium persulfate

CHID: 29698 CASRN: 7775-27-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M07

M4ID: 30006786

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.289 MAX_MED: 0.329 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fenofibrate

CHID: 29874 CASRN: 49562-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H05

M4ID: 30007292

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.335 MAX_MED: 0.312 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Perfluorooctanoic acid
 CHID: 31865 CASRN: 335-67-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G02
 M4ID: 30006935

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.151 MAX_MED: 0.118 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butralin

CHID: 32337 CASRN: 33629-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C17

M4ID: 30007016

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.163 MAX_MED: 0.135 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Clodinafop-propargyl

CHID: 32354 CASRN: 105512-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B04

M4ID: 30007053

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.144 MAX_MED: -0.0736 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Clomazone

CHID: 32355 CASRN: 81777-89-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P09

M4ID: 30007481

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.019 MAX_MED: 0.0458 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethenamid

CHID: 32376 CASRN: 87674-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G23

M4ID: 30006914

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.307 MAX_MED: 0.301 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethalfluralin

CHID: 32386 CASRN: 55283-68-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M22

M4ID: 30007540

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.269 MAX_MED: 0.22 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triclopyr

CHID: 32497 CASRN: 55335-06-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E06

M4ID: 30007363

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.045 MAX_MED: 0.0368 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxyethyl octyl sulfide

CHID: 32516 CASRN: 3547-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F16

M4ID: 30006945

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.293 MAX_MED: 0.353 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4,5-Dichloro-3H-1,2-dithiol-3-one

CHID: 32518 CASRN: 1192-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F24

M4ID: 30007321

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0816 MAX_MED: -0.07 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acibenzolar-S-methyl

CHID: 32519 CASRN: 135158-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A11

M4ID: 30007454

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.209 MAX_MED: 0.209 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Etridiazole

CHID: 32547 CASRN: 2593-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E08

M4ID: 30006977

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.169 MAX_MED: -0.14 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fenhexamid

CHID: 32549 CASRN: 126833-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E20

M4ID: 30007349

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.218 MAX_MED: 0.194 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Flufenacet

CHID: 32552 CASRN: 142459-58-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N16

M4ID: 30007137

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.352 MAX_MED: 0.201 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyridaben

CHID: 32573 CASRN: 96489-71-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M09

M4ID: 30006784

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.45 MAX_MED: 0.359 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tefluthrin

CHID: 32577 CASRN: 79538-32-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078013

M4ID: 30007116

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0893 MAX_MED: 0.113 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyproconazole

CHID: 32601 CASRN: 94361-06-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J03

M4ID: 30007246

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.324 MAX_MED: 0.302 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fenitrothion

CHID: 32613 CASRN: 122-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091018

M4ID: 30007496

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.373 MAX_MED: 0.314 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Flumetsulam

CHID: 32615 CASRN: 98967-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078016

M4ID: 30007113

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.24 MAX_MED: -0.128 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pymetrozine

CHID: 32637 CASRN: 123312-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I20

M4ID: 30007253

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.116 MAX_MED: 0.115 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyriproxyfen

CHID: 32640 CASRN: 95737-68-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G21

M4ID: 30006916

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.233 MAX_MED: 0.259 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamide

CHID: 32646 CASRN: 4151-50-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D04

M4ID: 30007389

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0757 MAX_MED: -0.0693 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Indoxacarb

CHID: 32690 CASRN: 173584-44-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H09

M4ID: 30007288

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.263 MAX_MED: 0.271 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Amino-1,2,4-triazole
 CHID: 33058 CASRN: 584-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P24
 M4ID: 30007466

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0533 MAX_MED: -0.0662 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyclopentanol

CHID: 33371 CASRN: 96-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A05

M4ID: 30007460

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.219 MAX_MED: 0.204 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Icaridin

CHID: 34227 CASRN: 119515-38-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A07

M4ID: 30007074

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.137 MAX_MED: 0.152 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tepraloxydim

CHID: 34252 CASRN: 149979-41-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C09

M4ID: 30007024

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.256 MAX_MED: 0.223 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Chlorophenoxyacetic acid

CHID: 34282 CASRN: 122-88-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N08

M4ID: 30007530

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0558 MAX_MED: 0.193 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Denatonium saccharide

CHID: 34361 CASRN: 90823-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D19

M4ID: 30006990

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0829 MAX_MED: 0.1 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Boscalid

CHID: 34392 CASRN: 188425-85-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B21

M4ID: 30007036

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0604 MAX_MED: 0.0128 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Buprofezin

CHID: 34401 CASRN: 69327-76-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091003

M4ID: 30007511

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.198 MAX_MED: 0.271 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butachlor

CHID: 34402 CASRN: 23184-66-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P11

M4ID: 30007479

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0546 MAX_MED: -0.0455 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cinmethylin

CHID: 34456 CASRN: 87818-31-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F20

M4ID: 30007325

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.12 MAX_MED: 0.156 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyhalofop-butyl

CHID: 34503 CASRN: 122008-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E21

M4ID: 30007348

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.152 MAX_MED: 0.147 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Desmedipham

CHID: 34518 CASRN: 13684-56-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M14

M4ID: 30007163

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.092 MAX_MED: 0.158 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dinotefuran

CHID: 34549 CASRN: 165252-70-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K08

M4ID: 30006833

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0247 MAX_MED: 0.0441 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Bromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone

CHID: 34576 CASRN: 2491-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D07

M4ID: 30007002

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0368 MAX_MED: 0.026 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Flufenpyr-ethyl

CHID: 34618 CASRN: 188489-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I07

M4ID: 30007266

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.306 MAX_MED: 0.277 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Imazamox

CHID: 34664 CASRN: 114311-32-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J07

M4ID: 30006858

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.197 MAX_MED: 0.206 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isazofos

CHID: 34676 CASRN: 42509-80-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I18

M4ID: 30006871

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.185 MAX_MED: 0.282 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isoxaflutole

CHID: 34723 CASRN: 141112-29-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091024

M4ID: 30007490

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.13 MAX_MED: 0.0265 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Penoxsulam

CHID: 34803 CASRN: 219714-96-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C18

M4ID: 30007399

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0268 MAX_MED: -0.0457 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Monocrotophos

CHID: 34816 CASRN: 6923-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091009

M4ID: 30007505

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.169 MAX_MED: 0.144 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propamocarb hydrochloride

CHID: 34849 CASRN: 25606-41-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F17

M4ID: 30006944

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.136 MAX_MED: 0.191 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluazifop-P-butyl

CHID: 34855 CASRN: 79241-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F09

M4ID: 30006952

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0446 MAX_MED: -0.0884 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Spiromesifen

CHID: 34929 CASRN: 283594-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G01

M4ID: 30007320

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.234 MAX_MED: 0.189 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fosthiazate

CHID: 34930 CASRN: 98886-44-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091022

M4ID: 30007492

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.266 MAX_MED: 0.164 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Thymo ℓ

CHID: 34972 CASRN: 89-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E13

M4ID: 30007356

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0491 MAX_MED: 0.0682 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tralkoxydim

CHID: 34973 CASRN: 87820-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L10

M4ID: 30006807

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0576 MAX_MED: 0.0646 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-(Hydroxymethyl)-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 35152 CASRN: 116-25-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D17

M4ID: 30006992

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.104 MAX_MED: 0.0468 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: alpha-Ionone

CHID: 35160 CASRN: 127-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D14

M4ID: 30007379

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.01 MAX_MED: -0.0095 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Allethrin

CHID: 35180 CASRN: 584-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P05

M4ID: 30007485

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0418 MAX_MED: 0.0111 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(8-Heptadecenyl)-2-imidazoline-1-ethanol

CHID: 36112 CASRN: 95-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K24

M4ID: 30006817

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.233 MAX_MED: 0.217 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Citralva

CHID: 36286 CASRN: 5146-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F12

M4ID: 30006949

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0506 MAX_MED: 0.00987 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fenuron

CHID: 37551 CASRN: 101-42-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K08

M4ID: 30007217

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.21 MAX_MED: 0.221 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate

CHID: 37709 CASRN: 3871-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091002

M4ID: 30007512

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.179 MAX_MED: 0.0464 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid

CHID: 38788 CASRN: 1076-97-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H12

M4ID: 30006901

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0541 MAX_MED: 0.0531 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluorescein

CHID: 38887 CASRN: 2321-07-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D24

M4ID: 30007369

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0676 MAX_MED: 0.0554 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethyl propionate

CHID: 40110 CASRN: 105-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B03

M4ID: 30007438

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0643 MAX_MED: 0.00321 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethyl heptanoate

CHID: 40112 CASRN: 106-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I16

M4ID: 30007257

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0642 MAX_MED: 0.0587 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Trifloxysulfuron-sodium

CHID: 40222 CASRN: 199119-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P23

M4ID: 30007467

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	34.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.282 MAX_MED: 0.105 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isoxadifen-ethyl

CHID: 40360 CASRN: 163520-33-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H13

M4ID: 30006900

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.333 MAX_MED: 0.332 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Niclosamide

CHID: 40362 CASRN: 50-65-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A24

M4ID: 30007057

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.188 MAX_MED: 0.216 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Forskolin

CHID: 40484 CASRN: 66575-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J23

M4ID: 30006842

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.225 MAX_MED: 0.33 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butyl benzoate

CHID: 40694 CASRN: 136-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B15

M4ID: 30007042

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0882 MAX_MED: 0.217 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Cyclohexylcyclohexanone

CHID: 40721 CASRN: 92-68-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F12

M4ID: 30007333

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0683 MAX_MED: 0.00502 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-methoxyphenol

CHID: 40788 CASRN: 121-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B02

M4ID: 30007055

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0569 MAX_MED: 0.0912 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium iodide

CHID: 41125 CASRN: 7681-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L12

M4ID: 30006805

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0446 MAX_MED: 0.018 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3,5-Triisopropylbenzene

CHID: 41232 CASRN: 717-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G12

M4ID: 30006925

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0444 MAX_MED: -0.035 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Hexyl-1-decanol

CHID: 41265 CASRN: 2425-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091012

M4ID: 30007502

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00337 MAX_MED: -0.0235 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Phenyl-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione

CHID: 41274 CASRN: 941-69-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C01

M4ID: 30007416

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.148 MAX_MED: 0.185 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 41306 CASRN: 131-55-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F11

M4ID: 30006950

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.303 MAX_MED: 0.246 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5-Ethyl-5-methylhydantoin

CHID: 41368 CASRN: 5394-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C16

M4ID: 30007401

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.207 MAX_MED: -0.112 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2'-Acetonaphthone

CHID: 41389 CASRN: 93-08-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G22

M4ID: 30007299

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0946 MAX_MED: -0.0312 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: R(-)-Carvone

CHID: 41413 CASRN: 6485-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E12

M4ID: 30006973

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.108 MAX_MED: -0.137 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Methylbutyl isovalerate

CHID: 41440 CASRN: 2445-77-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F11

M4ID: 30007334

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0137 MAX_MED: 0.0333 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: (3Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate

CHID: 41484 CASRN: 3681-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E23

M4ID: 30007346

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.125 MAX_MED: 0.132 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Morpholinepropanamine

CHID: 41521 CASRN: 123-00-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B10

M4ID: 30007431

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-31.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0064 MAX_MED: 0.00778 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dihydromyrcenol

CHID: 41557 CASRN: 53219-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L16

M4ID: 30007185

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.247 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pentyl butyrate

CHID: 41604 CASRN: 540-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A04

M4ID: 30007461

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.126 MAX_MED: -0.0674 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Arabinose

CHID: 41610 CASRN: 147-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C07

M4ID: 30007026

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.157 MAX_MED: 0.232 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benodanil

CHID: 41623 CASRN: 15310-01-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D15

M4ID: 30006994

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.166 MAX_MED: 0.23 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium m-xylene-4-sulfonate

CHID: 41639 CASRN: 827-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G20

M4ID: 30007301

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00525 MAX_MED: 0.00911 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 34, monosodium salt

CHID: 41646 CASRN: 6359-90-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E14

M4ID: 30007355

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00429 MAX_MED: 0.0404 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzyl cinnamate

CHID: 41663 CASRN: 103-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B20

M4ID: 30007421

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0294 MAX_MED: 0.00746 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butylphthalenesulfonic acid sodium salt

CHID: 41703 CASRN: 25638-17-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F05

M4ID: 30007340

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.241 MAX_MED: 0.192 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Citronellal

CHID: 41790 CASRN: 106-23-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C03

M4ID: 30007414

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.236 MAX_MED: 0.28 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dibutyl decanedioate

CHID: 41847 CASRN: 109-43-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E03

M4ID: 30007366

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0545 MAX_MED: 0.0256 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethyl phosphite

CHID: 41861 CASRN: 762-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N15

M4ID: 30007138

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.138 MAX_MED: 0.237 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethylbenzylcarbinyl acetate

CHID: 41877 CASRN: 151-05-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L15

M4ID: 30007186

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.291 MAX_MED: 0.278 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethyl diethanolamine
 CHID: 41955 CASRN: 139-87-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E19
 M4ID: 30006966

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0593 MAX_MED: 0.102 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethyl orthoformate

CHID: 41957 CASRN: 122-51-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P05

M4ID: 30007100

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-37.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0247 MAX_MED: -0.00308 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Flufenoxuron

CHID: 41978 CASRN: 101463-69-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E01

M4ID: 30007368

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.111 MAX_MED: 0.0762 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isobornyl propanoate

CHID: 42062 CASRN: 2756-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L11

M4ID: 30006806

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0984 MAX_MED: 0.107 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diphenylmercury(II)

CHID: 42130 CASRN: 587-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E12

M4ID: 30007357

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.121 MAX_MED: -0.163 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Dodecylmorpholine

CHID: 42171 CASRN: 1541-81-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A23

M4ID: 30007058

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.155 MAX_MED: 0.207 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N-Diisopropylaniline
 CHID: 42189 CASRN: 4107-98-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N08
 M4ID: 30007145

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.359 MAX_MED: 0.336 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Dimethylthiourea
 CHID: 42191 CASRN: 534-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091016
 M4ID: 30007498

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.236 MAX_MED: 0.175 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propylbenzene

CHID: 42219 CASRN: 103-65-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B11

M4ID: 30007430

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-63.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0834 MAX_MED: 0.0743 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethoxydimethylsilane
 CHID: 42379 CASRN: 1112-39-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I12
 M4ID: 30006877

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0953 MAX_MED: -0.0503 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium (2-pyridylthio)-N-oxide

CHID: 42390 CASRN: 3811-73-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E11

M4ID: 30007358

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.113 MAX_MED: 0.0889 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate

CHID: 42415 CASRN: 657-84-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C10

M4ID: 30007407

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00625 MAX_MED: 0.0289 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sulfosuccinic acid

CHID: 42426 CASRN: 5138-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P19

M4ID: 30007471

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.27 MAX_MED: 0.237 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester

CHID: 42454 CASRN: 589-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E14

M4ID: 30006971

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0603 MAX_MED: -0.0601 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Clove leaf oil

CHID: 44175 CASRN: 8000-34-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C09

M4ID: 30007408

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.168 MAX_MED: 0.204 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylethanone
 CHID: 44430 CASRN: 451-40-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L20
 M4ID: 30007181

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.128 MAX_MED: 0.239 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dibutyl-N-methylbutan-1-aminium chloride

CHID: 44443 CASRN: 56375-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P09

M4ID: 30007096

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0558 MAX_MED: 0.148 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 6:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 44572 CASRN: 647-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D02

M4ID: 30007007

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.116 MAX_MED: -0.0777 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-ethylphenol

CHID: 44581 CASRN: 96-70-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N04

M4ID: 30007534

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.249 MAX_MED: 0.134 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Terpinyl propionate

CHID: 44833 CASRN: 80-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P15

M4ID: 30007090

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.199 MAX_MED: -0.127 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triallyl trimellitate

CHID: 44901 CASRN: 2694-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H11

M4ID: 30006902

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0591 MAX_MED: 0.0657 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl triethanolamine titanate

CHID: 44928 CASRN: 36673-16-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C10

M4ID: 30007023

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.663 MAX_MED: 0.00223 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CI-1018

CHID: 47248 CASRN: NOCAS_47248

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F13

M4ID: 30006948

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.22 MAX_MED: 0.245 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-457920

CHID: 47254 CASRN: 220860-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N14

M4ID: 30007139

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0979 MAX_MED: 0.0533 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Zamifenacin

CHID: 47257 CASRN: 127308-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B24

M4ID: 30007417

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.117 MAX_MED: 0.0511 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CI-959

CHID: 47268 CASRN: 104795-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J09

M4ID: 30006856

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.374 MAX_MED: 0.254 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-409092

CHID: 47276 CASRN: 194098-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J01

M4ID: 30007248

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.412 MAX_MED: 0.354 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-457677

CHID: 47278 CASRN: 214535-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N01

M4ID: 30007152

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0832 MAX_MED: 0.0407 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: PHA-00543613

CHID: 47284 CASRN: 478149-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H01

M4ID: 30006912

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.261 MAX_MED: 0.2 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CI-1044

CHID: 47291 CASRN: NOCAS_47291

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G08

M4ID: 30007313

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0154 MAX_MED: 0.0387 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-863187

CHID: 47294 CASRN: 668981-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J14

M4ID: 30007235

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-38.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0806 MAX_MED: 0.041 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Zenarestat

CHID: 47296 CASRN: 112733-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L24

M4ID: 30007177

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.16 MAX_MED: 0.171 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-608039

CHID: 47305 CASRN: NOCAS_47305

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M02

M4ID: 30007175

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0455 MAX_MED: 0.101 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: UK-156819

CHID: 47309 CASRN: 162706-14-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N09

M4ID: 30007529

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.104 MAX_MED: 0.206 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: GW473178E methyl benzene sulphonic acid

CHID: 47313 CASRN: 263553-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C13

M4ID: 30007020

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.217 MAX_MED: 0.219 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: HMR1426

CHID: 47338 CASRN: 262376-75-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B04

M4ID: 30007437

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0657 MAX_MED: 0.0688 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SSR162369

CHID: 47346 CASRN: NOCAS_47346

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C05

M4ID: 30007412

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.234 MAX_MED: 0.212 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SSR150106

CHID: 47362 CASRN: NOCAS_47362

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E15

M4ID: 30007354

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.222 MAX_MED: 0.138 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Volinanserin

CHID: 47363 CASRN: 139290-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P13

M4ID: 30007477

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.134 MAX_MED: 0.21 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: AVE3295

CHID: 47372 CASRN: 478263-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K02

M4ID: 30007223

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.134 MAX_MED: 0.09 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SAR377142

CHID: 47385 CASRN: NOCAS_47385

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N17

M4ID: 30007521

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.371 MAX_MED: 0.246 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Grinstad Soft-N-Safe

CHID: 47394 CASRN: NOCAS_47394

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078008

M4ID: 30007121

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0797 MAX_MED: 0.175 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate

CHID: 47395 CASRN: 166412-78-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B03

M4ID: 30007054

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00179 MAX_MED: 0.00831 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dexamethasone sodium phosphate

CHID: 47429 CASRN: 2392-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H05

M4ID: 30006908

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0503 MAX_MED: 0.0407 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Potassium chlorate

CHID: 47448 CASRN: 3811-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H16

M4ID: 30006897

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.173 MAX_MED: 0.227 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexanedioic acid, di-C7-9-branched and linear ;

CHID: 47517 CASRN: 68515-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K09

M4ID: 30006832

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.194 MAX_MED: 0.118 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Adipic acid, polypropyleneglycol, laurate

CHID: 47527 CASRN: 66456-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L08

M4ID: 30007193

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.241 MAX_MED: 0.292 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Trioctyl trimellitate
 CHID: 47533 CASRN: 89-04-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L03
 M4ID: 30006814

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.192 MAX_MED: 0.341 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cremophor EL

CHID: 47696 CASRN: 61791-12-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L02

M4ID: 30007199

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.229 MAX_MED: 0.318 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Igepal CO-890

CHID: 47708 CASRN: NOCAS_47708

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J08

M4ID: 30007241

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.237 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Melengestrol acetate

CHID: 48184 CASRN: 2919-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C15

M4ID: 30007402

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.156 MAX_MED: 0.15 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl abietate

CHID: 48190 CASRN: 127-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I14

M4ID: 30006875

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.178 MAX_MED: 0.276 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Propylcyclohexanone

CHID: 48198 CASRN: 40649-36-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C14

M4ID: 30007403

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0848 MAX_MED: -0.0437 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48202 CASRN: 611-70-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G15

M4ID: 30007306

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.4 MAX_MED: 0.326 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl 2-methylbenzoate

CHID: 48208 CASRN: 89-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N04

M4ID: 30007149

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.091 MAX_MED: 0.203 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48509

CHID: 48509 CASRN: NOCAS_48509

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B15

M4ID: 30007426

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0136 MAX_MED: 0.119 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: HMR1171 trifluoroacetate (1:1)

CHID: 48522 CASRN: NOCAS_48522

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M08

M4ID: 30007169

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.229 MAX_MED: 0.237 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butylparaben
 CHID: 20209 CASRN: 94-26-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B17
 M4ID: 30007040

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.78e-14	1.1	1.33
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.1e-13	0.783	2.4	1.34	5.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.41	8.41	12.41
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.23	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.061 MAX_MED: 0.0203 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-tert-butylphenol

CHID: 20212 CASRN: 2409-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078002

M4ID: 30007127

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.126 MAX_MED: -0.184 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Butyrolactone

CHID: 20224 CASRN: 96-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N12

M4ID: 30007526

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0964 MAX_MED: 0.0703 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cupferron

CHID: 20352 CASRN: 135-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D16

M4ID: 30007377

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0286 MAX_MED: -0.00728 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dehydroepiandrosterone

CHID: 20379 CASRN: 53-43-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D18

M4ID: 30006991

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00396 MAX_MED: -0.0254 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dichlorvos

CHID: 20449 CASRN: 62-73-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D14

M4ID: 30006995

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0416 MAX_MED: 0.00311 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Maleic hydrazide

CHID: 20792 CASRN: 123-33-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C04

M4ID: 30007029

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.182 MAX_MED: -0.078 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl carbamate

CHID: 20834 CASRN: 598-55-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A22

M4ID: 30007059

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0987 MAX_MED: -0.0146 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nitrilotriacetic acid
 CHID: 20939 CASRN: 139-13-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A22
 M4ID: 30007443

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.13 MAX_MED: -0.0841 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propazine

CHID: 21196 CASRN: 139-40-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E18

M4ID: 30006967

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.147 MAX_MED: -0.155 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Trimethyl phosphate
 CHID: 21403 CASRN: 512-56-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F18
 M4ID: 30006943

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0884 MAX_MED: -0.0912 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 21520 CASRN: 143-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F16

M4ID: 30007329

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.073 MAX_MED: -0.146 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Decanal

CHID: 21553 CASRN: 112-31-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E24

M4ID: 30007345

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00113 MAX_MED: 0.00734 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dalapon

CHID: 21575 CASRN: 75-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P22

M4ID: 30007083

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.201 MAX_MED: -0.127 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Propanol

CHID: 21739 CASRN: 71-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N24

M4ID: 30007129

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.96e-12	0.449	1.3
sd:	8.28e-07	75100	687000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.19e-12	0.595	1.08	0.955	4.29
sd:	5.22e-07	69800	126000	65000	318000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.92	9.92	13.92
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.24	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.025 MAX_MED: 0.0982 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 21831 CASRN: 99-08-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B16

M4ID: 30007041

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0294 MAX_MED: 0.0135 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propoxur

CHID: 21948 CASRN: 114-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F08

M4ID: 30006953

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0891 MAX_MED: -0.128 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dibenzofuran
 CHID: 21993 CASRN: 132-64-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P14
 M4ID: 30007476

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.33e-12	-1.85	1.04
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.02e-09	-1.64	1.74	-1.32	4.95
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	46.78	52.78	56.78
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.46	0.46	0.46

MAX_MEAN: 0.128 MAX_MED: 0.096 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: DEET

CHID: 21995 CASRN: 134-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A08

M4ID: 30007073

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.205 MAX_MED: -0.192 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Hexyloxyaniline

CHID: 22288 CASRN: 39905-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P02

M4ID: 30007103

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.107 MAX_MED: -0.182 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,1,1-trichloroethane

CHID: 22325 CASRN: 2971-36-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B06

M4ID: 30007051

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.3 MAX_MED: 0.228 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 22406 CASRN: 131-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D24

M4ID: 30006985

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.151 MAX_MED: -0.17 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Digoxin

CHID: 22934 CASRN: 20830-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F14

M4ID: 30007331

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.85e-12	0.552	1.13
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.53e-12	0.876	1.33	1.21	4.12
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.17	18.17	22.17
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.27	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.0937 MAX_MED: 0.0515 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol tetranitrate

CHID: 23430 CASRN: 78-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F02

M4ID: 30006959

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0641 MAX_MED: -0.115 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Carboxin

CHID: 23951 CASRN: 5234-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C16

M4ID: 30007017

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0216 MAX_MED: -0.0293 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dicamba

CHID: 24018 CASRN: 1918-00-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A10

M4ID: 30007071

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.28e-12	-1.9	1.25
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.14e-12	-1.56	1.21	-0.906	5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.99	18.99	22.99
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.27	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: -0.0341 MAX_MED: 0.0173 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fomesafen

CHID: 24112 CASRN: 72178-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A16

M4ID: 30007065

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0546 MAX_MED: -0.0452 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methamidophos

CHID: 24177 CASRN: 10265-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A04

M4ID: 30007077

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.253 MAX_MED: -0.269 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzothiazole

CHID: 24586 CASRN: 95-16-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A02

M4ID: 30007463

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.187 MAX_MED: -0.119 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Carbendazim

CHID: 24729 CASRN: 10605-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P06

M4ID: 30007484

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0527 MAX_MED: -0.0985 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dicyclopentadiene

CHID: 25023 CASRN: 77-73-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E04

M4ID: 30007365

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.271 MAX_MED: -0.223 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl succinate

CHID: 25152 CASRN: 106-65-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A24

M4ID: 30007441

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0195 MAX_MED: 0.0403 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Theobromine

CHID: 26132 CASRN: 83-67-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P14

M4ID: 30007091

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.112 MAX_MED: -0.195 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acetyl tributyl citrate

CHID: 26446 CASRN: 77-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H16

M4ID: 30007281

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00222 MAX_MED: -0.0811 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phthalimide

CHID: 26514 CASRN: 85-41-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P08

M4ID: 30007482

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.126 MAX_MED: -0.162 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Pyridinecarbonitrile
 CHID: 26665 CASRN: 100-54-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B18
 M4ID: 30007039

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.12e-12	-0.609	0.927
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.03e-11	-0.00724	0.368	0.243	5.11
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.61	28.61	32.61
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.31	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: -0.0447 MAX_MED: 0.107 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phenyl phosphorus dichloride

CHID: 27282 CASRN: 644-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D20

M4ID: 30006989

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.018 MAX_MED: -0.101 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol

CHID: 27479 CASRN: 2440-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F15

M4ID: 30007330

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0167 MAX_MED: 0.00985 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-(Methylthio)propanal

CHID: 27528 CASRN: 3268-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A20

M4ID: 30007061

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	34.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.202 MAX_MED: -0.175 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dicyclohexyl sodium sulfosuccinate

CHID: 27826 CASRN: 23386-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M16

M4ID: 30007546

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.408 MAX_MED: 0.452 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8; 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,1-Bis(3,4-dimethylphenyl)ethane

CHID: 29223 CASRN: 1742-14-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B16

M4ID: 30007425

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0553 MAX_MED: 0.0274 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triethoxyoctylsilane

CHID: 29246 CASRN: 2943-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091008

M4ID: 30007506

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0275 MAX_MED: -0.147 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl stearate

CHID: 29304 CASRN: 11099-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D02

M4ID: 30007391

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0162 MAX_MED: 0.0162 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 8:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 29904 CASRN: 678-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E02

M4ID: 30006983

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.175 MAX_MED: -0.167 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Glycoluril

CHID: 31380 CASRN: 496-46-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G02

M4ID: 30007319

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0976 MAX_MED: -0.0628 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triclosan

CHID: 32498 CASRN: 3380-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091006

M4ID: 30007508

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.304 MAX_MED: 0.261 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Benzisothiazolin-3-one

CHID: 32523 CASRN: 2634-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E22

M4ID: 30007347

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0926 MAX_MED: -0.0759 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(Thiocyanomethylthio)benzothiazole

CHID: 32647 CASRN: 21564-17-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K10

M4ID: 30006831

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0523 MAX_MED: -0.128 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tetramethrin

CHID: 32649 CASRN: 7696-12-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091004

M4ID: 30007510

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0925 MAX_MED: -0.241 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Aldicarb sulfoxide

CHID: 33161 CASRN: 1646-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E16

M4ID: 30007353

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.193 MAX_MED: -0.0456 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 17-Methyltestosterone
 CHID: 33664 CASRN: 58-18-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A14
 M4ID: 30007067

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	39.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.215 MAX_MED: -0.165 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Haloperidol

CHID: 34150 CASRN: 52-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A14

M4ID: 30007451

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.129 MAX_MED: -0.0693 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluroxypyr-meptyl

CHID: 34303 CASRN: 81406-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A21

M4ID: 30007060

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.36e-12	0.498	1.31
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.21e-12	1.09	0.869	1.85	4.45
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.1	23.1	27.1
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.3	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: -0.0511 MAX_MED: 0.0147 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Chloridazon

CHID: 34872 CASRN: 1698-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E04

M4ID: 30006981

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.261 MAX_MED: -0.215 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyrimethanil

CHID: 34877 CASRN: 53112-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P04

M4ID: 30007486

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.208 MAX_MED: -0.208 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Thiamethoxam

CHID: 34962 CASRN: 153719-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A17

M4ID: 30007064

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.02e-13	0.932	1.25
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.93e-14	1.23	1.23	1.97	5.16
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.45	17.45	21.45
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.27	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.0225 MAX_MED: 0.0225 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Disodium 4,4'-bis(2-sulfostyryl)biphenyl

CHID: 36467 CASRN: 27344-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C12

M4ID: 30007021

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	68.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0625 MAX_MED: -0.0186 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Deisopropylatrazine

CHID: 37495 CASRN: 1007-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E03

M4ID: 30006982

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0367 MAX_MED: -0.0322 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Chlorpyrifos oxon

CHID: 38666 CASRN: 5598-15-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B10

M4ID: 30007047

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.126 MAX_MED: 0.0819 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethyl butyrate

CHID: 40111 CASRN: 105-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H02

M4ID: 30007295

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0128 MAX_MED: -0.0459 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Trimethoxyphenylsilane

CHID: 40700 CASRN: 2996-92-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D16

M4ID: 30006993

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.115 MAX_MED: -0.0506 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: (2-Nitro-1-propenyl)benzene

CHID: 41188 CASRN: 705-60-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F04

M4ID: 30007341

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.147 MAX_MED: -0.122 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 7-(Dimethylamino)-4-methylcoumarin

CHID: 41422 CASRN: 87-01-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D20

M4ID: 30007373

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	77.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.145 MAX_MED: -0.0703 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxybenzonitrile
 CHID: 41661 CASRN: 611-20-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G07
 M4ID: 30006930

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.5e-13	0.972	1.18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.95e-12	1.04	1.7	1.87	4.74
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.55	-7.55	-3.55
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.19	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.16 MAX_MED: 0.197 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diphenyl phosphite

CHID: 41889 CASRN: 4712-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E20

M4ID: 30006965

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.137 MAX_MED: -0.122 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluoroacetic acid

CHID: 41981 CASRN: 144-49-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B20

M4ID: 30007037

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.102 MAX_MED: 0.0425 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Dibutylthiourea
 CHID: 42187 CASRN: 109-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D12
 M4ID: 30006997

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0221 MAX_MED: -0.0458 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butyl lactate
 CHID: 42196 CASRN: 138-22-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A01
 M4ID: 30007464

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.32e-13	1.5	0.999
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.63e-12	1.81	1.1	2.25	4.3
sd:	1.01e-07	95900	317000	65800	1770000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.08	13.08	17.08
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.26	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 0.129 MAX_MED: 0.129 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Butyl-p-tuenesulfonamide

CHID: 42198 CASRN: 1907-65-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A16

M4ID: 30007449

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0965 MAX_MED: 0.0291 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Methyldioctylamine

CHID: 42209 CASRN: 4455-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091010

M4ID: 30007504

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.123 MAX_MED: -0.0524 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dibutyl nonanedioate

CHID: 44815 CASRN: 2917-73-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A02

M4ID: 30007079

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.128 MAX_MED: -0.0366 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylbenzene

CHID: 47138 CASRN: 98-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F02

M4ID: 30007343

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0708 MAX_MED: -0.124 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_47263

CHID: 47263 CASRN: 349495-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078024

M4ID: 30007105

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.155 MAX_MED: -0.164 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Besonprodil

CHID: 47270 CASRN: 253450-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E02

M4ID: 30007367

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.239 MAX_MED: -0.279 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: MK-812

CHID: 47335 CASRN: 851916-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A18

M4ID: 30007063

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.12 MAX_MED: -0.142 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SSR180711

CHID: 47359 CASRN: 298198-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P24

M4ID: 30007081

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.197 MAX_MED: -0.218 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SSR 103800

CHID: 47364 CASRN: 1075752-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P01

M4ID: 30007104

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.187 MAX_MED: 0.118 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: C10-21 alkanesulfonic acids phenyl esters

CHID: 47526 CASRN: 91082-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B09

M4ID: 30007432

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.06e-13	1.22	1.25
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.23e-11	1.54	1.18	2.05	5.13
sd:	2.88e-06	20400	590000	27100	613000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.76	-12.76	-8.76
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.17	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.00193 MAX_MED: 0.0716 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzyloctyl adipate

CHID: 47528 CASRN: 58394-64-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B14

M4ID: 30007043

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00889 MAX_MED: 0.0899 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octylparaben

CHID: 47957 CASRN: 1219-38-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B02

M4ID: 30007439

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.148 MAX_MED: 0.092 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyclobutyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48201 CASRN: 5407-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078014

M4ID: 30007115

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.122 MAX_MED: -0.133 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloropentylbenzene

CHID: 48206 CASRN: 79098-20-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C14

M4ID: 30007019

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.116 MAX_MED: -0.107 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium chloroacetate
 CHID: 27550 CASRN: 3926-62-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091020
 M4ID: 30007494

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.285	1.13	0.488
sd:	1.01	7.25	2.5

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.528	2.05	0.481	2.3	16.6
sd:	2.97	9.01	1.06	0.129	637

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.3	40.08	43.91
PROB:	0.78	0.19	0.03
RMSE:	0.41	0.38	0.38

MAX_MEAN: 0.293 MAX_MED: 0.515 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.22

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyridate

CHID: 32639 CASRN: 55512-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E13

M4ID: 30006972

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.833	2.31	7.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.226	2.25	0.3	3.52	6.34
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.12	21.81	28.56
PROB:	0.69	0.3	0.01
RMSE:	0.32	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.356 MAX_MED: 0.42 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.31

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluazifop-butyl

CHID: 34612 CASRN: 69806-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I17

M4ID: 30006872

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.326	2.8	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.705	2.08	7.97	2.33	6.77
sd:	6.78	0.818	18.1	1.96	149

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.97	-0.35	-1.3
PROB:	0.46	0.21	0.33
RMSE:	0.22	0.2	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.38 MAX_MED: 0.433 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.54

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Aniline hydrochloride
 CHID: 20091 CASRN: 142-04-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L10
 M4ID: 30007191

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.239	-2.38	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.238	-2.39	0.3	3.12	12.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.05	-11.66	-7.66
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.25	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.332 MAX_MED: 0.402 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzyl alcohol
 CHID: 20152 CASRN: 100-51-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N07
 M4ID: 30007146

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.287	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.287	-3.7	0.3	4.3	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.95	-34.24	-30.24
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.29	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.346 MAX_MED: 0.374 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Blue 74

CHID: 20190 CASRN: 860-22-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091019

M4ID: 30007495

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.29	-3.7	5.02
sd:	0.0603	302	1520

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.29	-3.65	5.83	3.34	7.88
sd:	0.0603	517	3160	1640	12500

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.87	27.23	31.23
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.41	0.32	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 0.533 MAX_MED: 0.462 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloroaniline

CHID: 20295 CASRN: 106-47-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H15

M4ID: 30006898

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.216	-3.7	0.503
sd:	0.0617	3.99	2.59

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.247	-3.7	0.3	4.05	0.384
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	18.49	-0.01	3.84
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.31	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.355 MAX_MED: 0.388 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl hydrogen phosphite

CHID: 20493 CASRN: 868-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J19

M4ID: 30006846

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.256	-2.33	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.256	-2.33	0.3	3.4	7.03
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.71	1.63	5.63
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.314 MAX_MED: 0.404 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diethyl phthalate

CHID: 21780 CASRN: 84-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J16

M4ID: 30006849

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.272	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.271	-3.7	0.3	4.3	12
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.98	-4.85	-0.85
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.4 MAX_MED: 0.46 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Undecanone

CHID: 21943 CASRN: 112-12-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L07

M4ID: 30007194

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.276	-2.98	3.48
sd:	0.0177	16.7	206

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.278	-3.7	0.818	4.29	8.16
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.43	-50.24	-46.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.28	0.09	0.09

MAX_MEAN: 0.38 MAX_MED: 0.393 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-(Dimethylamino)propylamine

CHID: 25102 CASRN: 109-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K01

M4ID: 30007224

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.268	-2.75	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.266	-2.84	0.3	4.3	5.07
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.55	-16.62	-12.62
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.29	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.477 MAX_MED: 0.429 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: tert-Nonanethiol

CHID: 27868 CASRN: 25360-10-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K23

M4ID: 30006818

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.292	-1.02	6.48
sd:	0.0649	2.42	818

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.292	-1.02	6.61	4.29	3.93
sd:	0.0649	2.48	871	2330	4640

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.02	24.44	28.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.41	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.517 MAX_MED: 0.673 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Profenofos

CHID: 32464 CASRN: 41198-08-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K05

M4ID: 30006836

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.291	-2.82	3.68
sd:	0.0559	44.4	1300

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.291	-2.83	3.65	2.78	17.8
sd:	0.0559	28.7	827	685	23100

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	34.81	23.41	27.41
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.38	0.32	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 0.372 MAX_MED: 0.466 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nilutamide

CHID: 34165 CASRN: 63612-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L06

M4ID: 30007195

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.222	-3.7	6.04
sd:	0.0237	333	2010

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.222	-3.7	6.22	2.87	17.2
sd:	0.0237	396	2470	774	21600

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.56	-21.1	-17.1
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.29	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.493 MAX_MED: 0.466 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene

CHID: 35423 CASRN: 571-58-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K21

M4ID: 30007204

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.186	-3.7	6.31
sd:	0.0372	592	3730

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.186	-3.68	6.05	4.3	3.93
sd:	0.0372	404	2480	1740	3430

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.43	1.49	5.49
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.28	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.409 MAX_MED: 0.456 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenylhexane

CHID: 41492 CASRN: 4468-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I09

M4ID: 30007264

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.196	-2.84	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.197	-2.83	0.3	3.34	8.87
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.31	-27.43	-23.43
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.22	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.409 MAX_MED: 0.453 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl monoricinoleate

CHID: 42007 CASRN: 1323-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M07

M4ID: 30007170

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.277	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.277	-3.7	0.3	4.29	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.68	-21.67	-17.67
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.568 MAX_MED: 0.561 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-671305

CHID: 47282 CASRN: 445295-04-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K07

M4ID: 30007218

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.226	-3.7	6.32
sd:	0.026	412	2610

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.226	-3.7	6.33	4.22	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.08	-20.68	-16.68
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.442 MAX_MED: 0.502 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-422935

CHID: 47299 CASRN: NOCAS_47299

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J01

M4ID: 30006864

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.267	-2.7	4.53
sd:	0.0261	0.605	533

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.267	-2.7	4.46	4.26	16.3
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.24	-23.29	-19.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.345 MAX_MED: 0.38 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Coumaphos

CHID: 20347 CASRN: 56-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K21

M4ID: 30006820

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.209	-2.69	3.77
sd:	0.0659	0.889	571

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.386	-1.97	0.715	1.01	18
sd:	0.163	1.53	1.06	0.171	238

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.68	25.4	26.35
PROB:	0.07	0.57	0.36
RMSE:	0.37	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.475 MAX_MED: 0.442 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 0.93

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bromoxynil

CHID: 22162 CASRN: 1689-84-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E21

M4ID: 30006964

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.243	-1.06	6.27
sd:	0.0477	9.8	952

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.676	2.3	0.3	4.22	7.7
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.18	4.88	8.05
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.3	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.383 MAX_MED: 0.412 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methylene bis(thiocyanate)

CHID: 25599 CASRN: 6317-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M19

M4ID: 30007158

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.237	-2.87	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.497	1.7	0.3	3.16	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.12	-0.7	5.03
PROB:	0	0.95	0.05
RMSE:	0.28	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.357 MAX_MED: 0.46 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Thiocarbazine

CHID: 27461 CASRN: 2231-57-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I20

M4ID: 30006869

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.133	-3.7	1.35
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.387	0.548	0.3	2.03	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.09	-10.53	-5.95
PROB:	0.02	0.89	0.09
RMSE:	0.21	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.253 MAX_MED: 0.401 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Propanediol monobutyl ether

CHID: 29755 CASRN: 29387-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I15

M4ID: 30007258

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.195	-2.5	3.83
sd:	0.0333	58.2	1120

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.476	-0.423	0.393	0.916	16
sd:	0.915	4.88	0.749	2.13	406

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.1	-10.42	-0.49
PROB:	0	0.99	0.01
RMSE:	0.24	0.17	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.361 MAX_MED: 0.377 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isoborneol

CHID: 42060 CASRN: 124-76-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091021

M4ID: 30007493

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.225	-3	3.16
sd:	0.0723	26.3	278

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.489	-2.68	4.94	0.693	0.3
sd:	1.22	1.23	374	8.13	0.865

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.42	30.76	33.82
PROB:	0.07	0.76	0.17
RMSE:	0.41	0.33	0.33

MAX_MEAN: 0.394 MAX_MED: 0.423 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 0.93

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Glycidyl trimethylammonium chloride

CHID: 44643 CASRN: 3033-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F21

M4ID: 30006940

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.264	-0.962	6.04
sd:	0.0598	5.53	875

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.523	1.12	0.3	2.33	17.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.05	17.36	21.48
PROB:	0.01	0.88	0.11
RMSE:	0.34	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.385 MAX_MED: 0.56 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48507

CHID: 48507 CASRN: NOCAS_48507

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I13

M4ID: 30006876

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.16	-2.72	3.92
sd:	0.0519	3.6	767

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.798	0.461	0.301	0.889	3.94
sd:	2.93	9.64	0.483	0.347	12.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.49	13.62	17.66
PROB:	0.17	0.73	0.1
RMSE:	0.3	0.25	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 0.315 MAX_MED: 0.526 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 0.83

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Propargite

CHID: 24276 CASRN: 2312-35-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D06

M4ID: 30007003

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.368	1.79	3.04
sd:	0.164	0.242	2.64

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.77e-11	-0.357	2.33	-0.0977	4.57
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	17.92	9.4	27.92
PROB:	0.01	0.99	0
RMSE:	0.3	0.24	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.375 MAX_MED: 0.32 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 18 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dichlobenil

CHID: 32365 CASRN: 1194-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L21

M4ID: 30007180

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.359	1.6	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.171	-2.71	0.3	4.28	4.95
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.45	4.47	7.95
PROB:	0.1	0.76	0.13
RMSE:	0.25	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 0.225 MAX_MED: 0.385 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 18 ACTP: 0.9

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octadecyl sulfate sodium salt

CHID: 47103 CASRN: 1120-04-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091013

M4ID: 30007501

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.293	-3.23	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.278	-2.74	3.51	4.27	12.3
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	46.57	40.91	44.91
PROB:	0.05	0.84	0.11
RMSE:	0.51	0.4	0.4

MAX_MEAN: 0.733 MAX_MED: 0.561 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 18 ACTP: 0.95

FLAGS: 8; 10; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 20494 CASRN: 756-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M20

M4ID: 30007542

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.365	-2.26	0.3
sd:	0.497	5.63	1.54

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.365	-2.27	0.3	3.99	3.04
sd:	0.503	5.68	1.56	297	530

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	39.96	29.5	33.5
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.42	0.32	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 0.404 MAX_MED: 0.6 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Eugenol

CHID: 20617 CASRN: 97-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K17

M4ID: 30007208

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.313	-2.93	3.36
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.313	-2.98	2.84	3.41	10.8
sd:	0.0257	10.4	107	26600	258000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.41	-25.74	-21.74
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.36	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.54 MAX_MED: 0.535 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5-Methyl-2-hexanone
 CHID: 21914 CASRN: 110-12-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K20
 M4ID: 30006821

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.294	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.298	-3.7	0.3	2.38	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.23	12.55	16.39
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.36	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 0.441 MAX_MED: 0.571 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diphenolic acid

CHID: 22436 CASRN: 126-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L13

M4ID: 30006804

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.317	-3.01	3.29
sd:	0.0665	44.6	472

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.328	-2.99	3.06	2.54	2.54
sd:	0.0842	20.4	217	1.75	16.9

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	41.3	25.53	29.43
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.45	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.471 MAX_MED: 0.64 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benz(a)anthracene
 CHID: 23902 CASRN: 56-55-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K02
 M4ID: 30006839

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.353	-0.765	0.3
sd:	0.216	2.24	0.431

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.353	-0.765	0.3	3.41	7.03
sd:	0.216	2.24	0.431	1080	6870

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.68	-7.65	-3.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.26	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.375 MAX_MED: 0.375 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: MCPB
 CHID: 24193 CASRN: 94-81-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K13
 M4ID: 30006828

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.349	-2.75	3.94
sd:	0.0517	3.04	257

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.349	-2.72	7.69	3.86	5.07
sd:	0.0517	0.295	94.6	1450	4720

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.76	14.89	18.89
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.46	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.633 MAX_MED: 0.476 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Terbaci1

CHID: 24317 CASRN: 5902-51-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K05

M4ID: 30007220

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.301	-3.7	0.853
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.301	-3.7	0.853	4.28	6.78
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.68	-37.6	-33.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.32	0.11	0.11

MAX_MEAN: 0.399 MAX_MED: 0.421 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene

CHID: 25132 CASRN: 83-41-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L01

M4ID: 30006816

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.32	-3.7	6.33
sd:	0.0358	258	1640

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.32	-3.7	6.59	4.05	10.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.4	-7.14	-3.14
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.37	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.44 MAX_MED: 0.483 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Methylbutyl acetate
 CHID: 25453 CASRN: 123-92-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M17
 M4ID: 30007160

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.349	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.349	-3.7	0.3	3.71	8.01
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.46	-13.64	-9.64
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.36	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.594 MAX_MED: 0.595 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 26224 CASRN: 112-49-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M01

M4ID: 30006792

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.33	-2.71	4.43
sd:	0.0288	0.826	294

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.33	-2.71	3.81	3.77	6.43
sd:	0.0288	0.965	252	3890	17000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.91	-16.8	-12.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.36	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.583 MAX_MED: 0.577 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ammonium carbamate
 CHID: 27360 CASRN: 1111-78-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N05
 M4ID: 30007148

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.305	-3.7	0.89
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.346	-3.7	0.3	2.61	1.68
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.67	-21.71	-18.51
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.31	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.384 MAX_MED: 0.43 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylacetamide

CHID: 27454 CASRN: 2044-64-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L05

M4ID: 30006812

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.298	-2.85	3.31
sd:	0.0691	70.6	1590

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.298	-2.86	3.08	3.97	15.4
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	39.35	31.72	35.72
PROB:	0.02	0.86	0.12
RMSE:	0.41	0.35	0.35

MAX_MEAN: 0.312 MAX_MED: 0.536 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Butylene carbonate
 CHID: 40342 CASRN: 4437-85-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L19
 M4ID: 30006798

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.297	-1.18	5.92
sd:	0.0485	42.8	1410

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.319	-1.15	5.4	2.32	17.5
sd:	0.053	12.9	465	0.0401	49.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.22	7.69	10.79
PROB:	0	0.82	0.17
RMSE:	0.35	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.354 MAX_MED: 0.436 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: UK-416244

CHID: 47290 CASRN: 402910-27-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M13

M4ID: 30006780

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.366	-2.96	3.32
sd:	0.0543	27.3	345

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.366	-2.95	3.49	4.11	3.65
sd:	0.0543	65.2	912	1690	3220

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	45.45	17.43	21.43
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.48	0.28	0.28

MAX_MEAN: 0.542 MAX_MED: 0.467 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Butylphenol

CHID: 47425 CASRN: 1638-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M09

M4ID: 30007168

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.357	-3.06	0.867
sd:	0.0299	1.05	2.31

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.357	-3.06	0.867	4.15	17.7
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.79	-17.86	-13.86
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.4	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.715 MAX_MED: 0.769 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Endrin

CHID: 20561 CASRN: 72-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F15

M4ID: 30006946

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.316	1.21	0.857
sd:	0.159	0.694	1.09

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.755	2.12	0.671	2.37	2.34
sd:	2.15	3.06	0.744	0.424	4.18

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.1	-10.63	-7.33
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	0.27	0.18	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.48 MAX_MED: 0.48 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isophorone

CHID: 20759 CASRN: 78-59-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L05

M4ID: 30007196

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.357	-3.7	1.07
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.391	-3.7	0.3	2.33	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.02	-15.83	-12.69
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.39	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.531 MAX_MED: 0.419 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodibutylamine
 CHID: 21026 CASRN: 924-16-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J15
 M4ID: 30006850

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.363	-2.89	3.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.01	-1.33	0.3	0.825	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.23	8.62	13.64
PROB:	0	0.92	0.08
RMSE:	0.44	0.23	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.456 MAX_MED: 0.426 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diisopropyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 24051 CASRN: 1445-75-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091015

M4ID: 30007499

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.328	-2.96	3.56
sd:	0.0675	25.5	347

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.537	-2.72	6.57	1.76	0.3
sd:	0.593	0.265	91.9	3.38	0.681

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	45.22	27.41	30.29
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	0.49	0.32	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 0.542 MAX_MED: 0.472 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: (4Z)-4-Decenal

CHID: 41514 CASRN: 21662-09-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K09

M4ID: 30007216

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.351	-3.7	0.611
sd:	0.0373	2.85	2.46

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.431	-1.07	4.56	3.74	0.3
sd:	0.656	1.6	102	4.7	2.41

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.69	-27.45	-11.43
PROB:	0	1	0
RMSE:	0.38	0.15	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.47 MAX_MED: 0.441 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-(6-tert-Butyl-1,1-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-im

CHID: 44536 CASRN: 13171-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M21

M4ID: 30007541

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.293	-3.12	0.892
sd:	0.08	3.64	6.85

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.846	-0.626	0.3	1.07	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	44.76	35.85	40.46
PROB:	0.01	0.9	0.09
RMSE:	0.48	0.36	0.37

MAX_MEAN: 0.514 MAX_MED: 0.457 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tromethamine
 CHID: 23723 CASRN: 77-86-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M15
 M4ID: 30007162

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.504	2.02	7.12
sd:	0.133	0.0766	8.49

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.212	-2.84	4.11	4.21	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.92	12.97	12.4
PROB:	0.01	0.42	0.56
RMSE:	0.31	0.26	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.508 MAX_MED: 0.446 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 27 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tributyl phosphate
 CHID: 21986 CASRN: 126-73-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K01
 M4ID: 30006840

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.957	1.87	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.362	-2.85	3.45	2.87	17.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	40.99	2.27	-6.96
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	0.43	0.21	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.825 MAX_MED: 0.871 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 32 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Nitroaniline
 CHID: 25726 CASRN: 88-74-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N01
 M4ID: 30007537

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.756	1.65	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.314	-3.7	6.99	4.3	15.4
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.96	-3.43	-6.52
PROB:	0	0.18	0.82
RMSE:	0.38	0.2	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.633 MAX_MED: 0.68 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 32 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyl methanesulfonate

CHID: 20845 CASRN: 66-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N15

M4ID: 30007523

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.429	-2.93	5.25
sd:	0.0604	6.22	139

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.569	-2.75	7.97	2.87	0.3
sd:	0.422	0.249	37.9	1.85	0.844

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	53.68	19.85	22.81
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	0.54	0.28	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.588 MAX_MED: 0.542 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 36 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexamethyleneimine
 CHID: 26879 CASRN: 111-49-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M19
 M4ID: 30007543

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.384	-3.7	6.22
sd:	0.0458	369	2290

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.384	-3.7	6.22	3.82	5.33
sd:	0.0458	367	2280	1390	4870

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.91	13.01	17.01
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.44	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 0.65 MAX_MED: 0.652 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 36 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium warfarin

CHID: 35010 CASRN: 129-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L17

M4ID: 30007184

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.397	-3.65	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.397	-3.64	0.3	4.24	4.27
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.01	-34.07	-30.07
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.39	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.528 MAX_MED: 0.495 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 36 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Perfluoroheptanoic acid

CHID: 37303 CASRN: 375-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N16

M4ID: 30007522

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.415	-2.8	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.415	-2.8	0.3	3.76	5.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	44.94	13.28	17.28
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.47	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 0.553 MAX_MED: 0.5 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 36 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,6,10-Trimethyl-2,6,10-triazaundecane

CHID: 44564 CASRN: 3855-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L15

M4ID: 30006802

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.428	-3.69	6.94
sd:	0.0491	595	4180

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.428	-3.69	6.49	2.98	12.7
sd:	0.0491	373	2450	1390	25900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	49.96	11.44	15.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.5	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.533 MAX_MED: 0.598 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 36 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethoxyquin

CHID: 20582 CASRN: 91-53-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G19

M4ID: 30007302

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.405	2.02	8
sd:	0.0742	0.0422	5.48

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.563	2.04	8	2.41	3.55
sd:	2.32	0.333	5.58	2.57	29.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.68	-29.88	-25.97
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.17	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.309 MAX_MED: 0.423 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octadecanoic acid
 CHID: 21642 CASRN: 57-11-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K07
 M4ID: 30006834

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.404	1.99	8
sd:	0.0905	0.0646	11.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.404	1.99	8	4.14	7.47
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.64	-1.27	2.73
PROB:	0.03	0.86	0.12
RMSE:	0.25	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 0.397 MAX_MED: 0.44 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Aldoxycarb

CHID: 23862 CASRN: 1646-88-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078001

M4ID: 30007128

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.421	2.01	8
sd:	0.134	0.0782	9.36

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.714	2.05	7.96	2.31	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.1	3.88	7.72
PROB:	0.15	0.74	0.11
RMSE:	0.25	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.383 MAX_MED: 0.447 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 0.85

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Hydroxypyrene

CHID: 38298 CASRN: 5315-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H20

M4ID: 30007277

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.37	1.67	8
sd:	0.0772	0.0857	11.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.37	1.67	8	4.3	3.7
sd:	0.0772	0.0857	11.9	1010	1900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.58	-8.32	-4.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.474 MAX_MED: 0.58 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 7-Ethyl-2-methyl-4-undecanolsulfate, sodium sa

CHID: 41530 CASRN: 139-88-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N19

M4ID: 30007519

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.433	-2.14	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.943	0.456	0.3	2.51	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	44.52	24.77	29.74
PROB:	0	0.92	0.08
RMSE:	0.46	0.3	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.509 MAX_MED: 0.667 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bromophenol blue
 CHID: 41682 CASRN: 115-39-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C02
 M4ID: 30007415

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.427	1.97	8
sd:	0.0968	0.0528	6.78

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.652	1.99	8	2.64	0.809
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	11.27	1.41	5.36
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.423 MAX_MED: 0.37 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexanedinitrile

CHID: 21936 CASRN: 111-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M14

M4ID: 30007548

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.413	0.588	0.3
sd:	0.795	6.59	0.669

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.413	0.588	0.3	3.64	6.78
sd:	0.795	6.59	0.669	19600	99400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.49	16.88	20.88
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.36	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.338 MAX_MED: 0.415 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tri-allate

CHID: 24344 CASRN: 2303-17-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K16

M4ID: 30006825

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.408	-1.15	0.3
sd:	0.239	2.28	0.483

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.408	-1.15	0.3	3.58	6.36
sd:	0.239	2.28	0.482	1680	8340

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.23	-4.02	-0.02
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.37	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.429 MAX_MED: 0.437 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4,5-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 24359 CASRN: 95-95-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J22
 M4ID: 30006843

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.384	1.43	0.592
sd:	0.612	2.67	1.23

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.839	1.95	3.08	2.2	6.46
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.43	22.51	24.87
PROB:	0.15	0.65	0.2
RMSE:	0.35	0.29	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 0.434 MAX_MED: 0.471 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 0.85

FLAGS: 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dodecylbenzene sulfonate triethanolamine(1:1)

CHID: 27932 CASRN: 27323-41-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C01

M4ID: 30007032

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.423	2.18	8
sd:	2.17	2.15	57.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.423	2.18	8	3.21	3.82
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.69	-24.57	-20.57
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.18	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.384 MAX_MED: 0.388 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Heptanolid

CHID: 47611 CASRN: 105-21-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J13

M4ID: 30006852

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.39	-0.484	0.3
sd:	0.347	3.45	0.525

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.434	-0.0557	0.3	2.32	18
sd:	0.737	6.21	0.71	0.0616	50

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.37	9.05	12.76
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	0.36	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.417 MAX_MED: 0.577 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-(Butan-2-yl)phenol
 CHID: 22331 CASRN: 89-72-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K15
 M4ID: 30006826

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.453	-3.5	0.653
sd:	0.0512	3.18	2.55

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.453	-3.5	0.653	4.3	9.05
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	50.04	4.8	8.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.5	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 0.709 MAX_MED: 0.745 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 40 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzoic acid
 CHID: 38321 CASRN: 3739-38-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M15
 M4ID: 30007547

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.444	-2.92	3.62
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.444	-2.92	3.53	4.02	6.64
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	54.19	19.39	23.39
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.54	0.28	0.28

MAX_MEAN: 0.647 MAX_MED: 0.571 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 40 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Amino-5-azotoluene
 CHID: 20069 CASRN: 97-56-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F22
 M4ID: 30007323

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.28	1.94	6.97
sd:	0.124	0.0263	4.66

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.74	1.99	5.08	2.33	16.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	50.9	7.55	11.19
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	0.57	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 1.28 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylhydroquinone
 CHID: 20220 CASRN: 1948-33-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C21
 M4ID: 30007396

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.682	1.92	5.47
sd:	0.132	0.0801	14.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.04	2	4.19	2.32	11.8
sd:	1.17	0.221	2.98	0.054	38.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.43	-16.62	-13.43
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.31	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.628 MAX_MED: 0.648 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: o,p'-DDD

CHID: 20372 CASRN: 53-19-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K19

M4ID: 30007206

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.01	2.04	5.08
sd:	0.242	0.0881	3.36

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.35	2.05	5.07	3.9	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.25	16.67	20.68
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.39	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.781 MAX_MED: 0.999 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

CHID: 20375 CASRN: 50-29-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E17

M4ID: 30006968

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.602	2.09	6.14
sd:	0.148	0.122	5.62

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.602	2.09	6.14	2.69	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.17	-15.89	-11.89
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.25	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.577 MAX_MED: 0.549 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 17alpha-Ethinylestradiol

CHID: 20576 CASRN: 57-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J08

M4ID: 30006857

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.881	1.93	8
sd:	0.229	0.049	7.11

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.56	2.02	5.16	2.31	17.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.63	26.68	30.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.47	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.83 MAX_MED: 0.881 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,2'-Methylenebis(4-methyl-6-tert-butylphenol)

CHID: 20870 CASRN: 119-47-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P16

M4ID: 30007089

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.06	1.64	8
sd:	0.133	0.0534	7.26

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.06	1.64	8	4.07	4.84
sd:	0.133	0.0534	7.26	3020	8290

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.88	35.93	39.93
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.83	0.37	0.37

MAX_MEAN: 3.05 MAX_MED: 3.26 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nitrofurantoin
 CHID: 20972 CASRN: 67-20-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H02
 M4ID: 30006911

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.725	1.33	2.54
sd:	0.074	0.0855	1.44

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.866	1.39	2.38	2.44	5.04
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.07	-13.99	-10
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.25	0.1	0.1

MAX_MEAN: 0.722 MAX_MED: 0.722 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phenylmercuric acetate

CHID: 21150 CASRN: 62-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E09

M4ID: 30006976

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.65	1.71	8
sd:	0.0709	0.0122	2.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.67	1.71	8	2.4	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	130.75	13.59	17.4
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	2.08	0.32	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 3.64 MAX_MED: 3.65 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triphenyltin hydroxide

CHID: 21409 CASRN: 76-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I21

M4ID: 30007252

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.67	1.04	4.35
sd:	0.0734	0.0273	1.51

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.67	1.04	4.35	4.05	4.75
sd:	0.0734	0.0273	1.51	1490	4080

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.12	37.63	41.63
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.67	0.54	0.54

MAX_MEAN: 3.71 MAX_MED: 3.73 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: FD&C Yellow 5

CHID: 21455 CASRN: 1934-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C18

M4ID: 30007015

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.47	1.9	3.37
sd:	0.229	0.0591	1.55

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.06	1.99	2.82	2.35	10.6
sd:	3.07	0.433	2	0.0758	27.4

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	64.35	23.06	26.57
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	0.68	0.3	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 1.41 MAX_MED: 1.26 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ziram
 CHID: 21464 CASRN: 137-30-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A08
 M4ID: 30007457 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.6	1.22	8
sd:	0.112	0.0478	3.33

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.6	1.22	8	2.97	13.3
sd:	0.112	0.0478	3.33	737	14500

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	103.94	40.05	44.05
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.34	0.54	0.54

MAX_MEAN: 2.8 MAX_MED: 3.38 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dichlorophen

CHID: 21824 CASRN: 97-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N13

M4ID: 30007525

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.97	1.88	4.57
sd:	0.309	0.0371	1.51

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.07	1.94	4.06	2.35	10.9
sd:	2.19	0.103	1.59	0.0267	12.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	119.49	62.63	64.85
PROB:	0	0.75	0.25
RMSE:	1.8	0.57	0.55

MAX_MEAN: 3.83 MAX_MED: 3.73 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Phenol red
 CHID: 22408 CASRN: 143-74-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A06
 M4ID: 30007075

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.448	1.99	8
sd:	0.145	0.0691	7.78

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.751	2.03	8	2.31	15.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.11	17.79	21.61
PROB:	0.14	0.75	0.11
RMSE:	0.32	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.42 MAX_MED: 0.47 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 0.86

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexylparaben
 CHID: 22525 CASRN: 5153-25-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L11
 M4ID: 30007190

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.83	1.79	8
sd:	0.0687	0.00924	0.707

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.83	1.79	8	4.24	5.16
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.53	-17.44	-13.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.01	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 3.78 MAX_MED: 3.83 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tetracycline
 CHID: 23645 CASRN: 60-54-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C11
 M4ID: 30007406

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.47	1.95	8
sd:	0.0413	0.0175	2.71

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.613	1.98	7.94	2.35	9.28
sd:	0.131	0.0254	2.22	0.0409	10.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.76	-55.12	-53.45
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	0.19	0.09	0.09

MAX_MEAN: 0.406 MAX_MED: 0.445 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dinitrobenzene
 CHID: 24065 CASRN: 99-65-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N14
 M4ID: 30007524

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.54	1.37	1.63
sd:	0.214	0.364	2.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.2	2.04	0.875	2.31	17
sd:	3.2	2.3	0.87	0.0486	107

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	43.09	26.74	29.85
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.47	0.33	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 0.601 MAX_MED: 0.653 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octhilinone

CHID: 25805 CASRN: 26530-20-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L06

M4ID: 30006811

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.39	1.94	8
sd:	0.24	0.0243	4.89

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.39	1.94	8	4.1	7.93
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	82.02	50.6	54.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.01	0.51	0.51

MAX_MEAN: 2.28 MAX_MED: 2.46 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,10-Phenanthroline
 CHID: 25857 CASRN: 66-71-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H18
 M4ID: 30006895

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.785	1.08	2.79
sd:	0.0565	0.088	1.81

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.785	1.08	2.79	4.22	4.4
sd:	0.0565	0.088	1.81	1810	4170

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	56	-10.35	-6.35
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.56	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.871 MAX_MED: 0.925 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium dodecyl sulfate
 CHID: 26031 CASRN: 151-21-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H22
 M4ID: 30007275

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.53	2.03	7.33
sd:	0.129	0.0194	1.72

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.3	2.04	7.3	4.1	0.367
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	80.49	15.46	19.45
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.23	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 3.48 MAX_MED: 3.57 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-pentylphenol
 CHID: 26974 CASRN: 120-95-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L16
 M4ID: 30006801

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.88	1.86	4.56
sd:	0.218	0.0293	1.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.72	1.9	4.15	2.34	18
sd:	1.25	0.0669	1.04	0.0105	15

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	116.66	48.36	48.72
PROB:	0	0.54	0.46
RMSE:	1.77	0.49	0.46

MAX_MEAN: 3.72 MAX_MED: 3.81 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dibutyltin dichloride
 CHID: 27292 CASRN: 683-18-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H06
 M4ID: 30006907

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.16	0.903	3.23
sd:	0.0848	0.0397	0.752

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.16	0.903	3.23	2.87	16.1
sd:	0.0848	0.0397	0.752	439	12000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.55	23.06	27.06
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.3	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 3.22 MAX_MED: 3.34 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Iodo-2-propynyl-N-butylcarbamate
 CHID: 28038 CASRN: 55406-53-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M23
 M4ID: 30007154

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.77 1.99 8
 sd: 0.13 0.00967 1.41

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.69 2.01 8 2.37 8.66
 sd: 0.584 0.0108 1.17 0.0122 4.09

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	87.16	17.65	20.15
PROB:	0	0.78	0.22
RMSE:	1.34	0.34	0.34

MAX_MEAN: 3.73 MAX_MED: 3.74 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol

CHID: 29241 CASRN: 2772-45-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J04

M4ID: 30006861

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.2	1.81	8
sd:	0.122	0.0208	1.72

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.2	1.81	8	3.61	9.54
sd:	0.122	0.0208	1.72	84500	620000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	112.14	17.33	21.33
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.6	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 2.9 MAX_MED: 3.29 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium lauryl polyoxyethylene ether sulfate

CHID: 29298 CASRN: 9004-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J21

M4ID: 30007228

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.85	1.99	8
sd:	0.147	0.0329	4.04

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.72	1.99	8	4.19	0.342
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	99.64	24.85	28.65
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	1.53	0.35	0.34

MAX_MEAN: 3.81 MAX_MED: 3.89 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Perfluorononanoic acid
 CHID: 31863 CASRN: 375-95-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C02
 M4ID: 30007031

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.783	2.05	8
sd:	0.189	0.145	9.79

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.24	2.08	7.91	2.33	8.92
sd:	4.15	0.244	8.93	0.211	87.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.73	15.37	19.28
PROB:	0.21	0.69	0.1
RMSE:	0.33	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.588 MAX_MED: 0.763 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 0.79

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bifenazate

CHID: 32525 CASRN: 149877-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G22

M4ID: 30006915

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.7	1.89	8
sd:	0.106	0.103	16.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.944	1.94	6.17	2.32	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.61	10.97	14.22
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	0.4	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 0.679 MAX_MED: 0.674 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluazinam

CHID: 32551 CASRN: 79622-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A01

M4ID: 30007080

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.61	2.03	6.52
sd:	0.177	0.0194	1.65

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.28	2.03	6.47	4.28	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	64.72	3.81	7.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.93	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 2.68 MAX_MED: 2.59 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Prallethrin
 CHID: 32572 CASRN: 23031-36-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078019
 M4ID: 30007110

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.589	1.99	8
sd:	0.115	0.0383	4.74

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.625	1.99	8	2.37	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.91	-15.67	-11.67
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.614 MAX_MED: 0.583 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Metconazole

CHID: 34497 CASRN: 125116-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078011

M4ID: 30007118

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.586	1.95	4.97
sd:	0.0766	0.0412	2.39

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.586	1.95	4.97	4.23	2.81
sd:	0.077	0.0413	2.39	1280	1940

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.52	-34.4	-30.4
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.26	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.556 MAX_MED: 0.612 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diclosulam

CHID: 34528 CASRN: 145701-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K23

M4ID: 30007202

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.529	2.01	8
sd:	0.113	0.0673	8.61

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.785	2.04	7.96	2.33	11.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.31	2.83	6.78
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.521 MAX_MED: 0.544 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Milbemectin (mixture of 70% Milbemcin A4, 30% I

CHID: 34742 CASRN: NOCAS_34742

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D01

M4ID: 30007008

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.443	1.9	8
sd:	0.09	0.0484	7.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.443	1.9	8	3.88	9.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.37	-20.96	-16.96
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.26	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.521 MAX_MED: 0.481 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Azamethiphos
 CHID: 34818 CASRN: 35575-96-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K03
 M4ID: 30006838

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.826	1.94	8
sd:	0.132	0.0376	6.18

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.32	2	7.35	2.32	13.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	34.65	9.28	12.96
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	0.42	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.834 MAX_MED: 0.706 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Codlelure

CHID: 35288 CASRN: 33956-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I01

M4ID: 30007272

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.703	2.03	7.2
sd:	0.095	0.0553	5.81

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.703	2.03	7.2	3.53	8.02
sd:	0.095	0.0553	5.81	128000	835000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.17	-12.38	-8.38
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.28	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.689 MAX_MED: 0.731 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methylbenzethonium chloride

CHID: 35708 CASRN: 25155-18-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D10

M4ID: 30006999

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.63	1.48	4.4
sd:	0.0558	0.019	0.423

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.63	1.48	4.4	4.03	5.21
sd:	0.0558	0.019	0.423	1810	5450

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.25	4.18	8.18
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.3	0.48	0.48

MAX_MEAN: 3.68 MAX_MED: 3.62 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Basic Blue 7

CHID: 38888 CASRN: 2390-60-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K11

M4ID: 30006830

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.25	1.56	2.83
sd:	0.141	0.0391	0.416

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.25	1.69	2.11	2.63	2.17
sd:	3.66	0.296	1.2	2.16	18.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.91	33.82	37.05
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	2.31	0.6	0.52

MAX_MEAN: 4.18 MAX_MED: 4.16 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Diniconazole
 CHID: 40363 CASRN: 83657-24-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C06
 M4ID: 30007027

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.65	2.02	6.97
sd:	0.179	0.0255	2.95

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.71	2.06	6.15	2.33	13.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	73.08	13.56	17.45
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.99	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 2.69 MAX_MED: 2.57 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanedione

CHID: 41247 CASRN: 120-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A17

M4ID: 30007448

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.477	2.06	8
sd:	0.0905	0.0869	8.82

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.805	2.07	8	2.57	0.616
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.46	-22.75	-18.75
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.21	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.496 MAX_MED: 0.424 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 3 disodium salt

CHID: 41721 CASRN: 8004-92-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F14

M4ID: 30006947

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.449	1.93	8
sd:	0.116	0.0505	4.93

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.449	1.93	8	3.4	6.32
sd:	0.116	0.0505	4.93	1960	11400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.49	-5.72	-1.72
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.457 MAX_MED: 0.448 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Oleyl sarcosine

CHID: 42243 CASRN: 110-25-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I11

M4ID: 30006878

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.538	1.99	8
sd:	0.104	0.0381	4.45

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.929	2.03	8	2.31	11.2
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.44	-10.24	-6.85
PROB:	0	0.84	0.15
RMSE:	0.27	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.549 MAX_MED: 0.475 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium tridecyl sulfate

CHID: 42418 CASRN: 3026-63-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P04

M4ID: 30007101

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.54	1.93	8
sd:	0.213	0.0187	2.83

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.54	1.93	8	3.36	10.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	105.76	40.76	44.76
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.54	0.41	0.41

MAX_MEAN: 3.4 MAX_MED: 3.32 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Methyltrioctylammonium chloride

CHID: 44487 CASRN: 5137-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A09

M4ID: 30007456

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.5	1.4	2.66
sd:	0.141	0.0885	0.528

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.5	1.4	2.66	3.95	4.6
sd:	0.141	0.0885	0.528	1530	4200

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.06	36.92	40.92
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.24	0.52	0.52

MAX_MEAN: 3.51 MAX_MED: 3.43 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,2'-(Tetradecylimino)diethanol

CHID: 44865 CASRN: 18924-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D10

M4ID: 30007383

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.33	1.99	4.41
sd:	0.519	0.0882	2.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.33	1.99	4.41	4.28	3.45
sd:	0.519	0.0882	2.2	1410	2550

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	70.76	50.92	54.92
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.93	0.52	0.52

MAX_MEAN: 2.07 MAX_MED: 2.21 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SR125047

CHID: 47342 CASRN: NOCAS_47342

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F01

M4ID: 30007344

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.499	2.09	8
sd:	0.158	0.266	17.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.499	2.09	8	4.3	6.73
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.33	-11.44	-7.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.23	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.492 MAX_MED: 0.454 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acid Yellow 11

CHID: 47451 CASRN: 6359-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A13

M4ID: 30007068

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.539	2.12	8
sd:	0.381	0.506	26.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.663	2.13	8	2.38	8.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.44	2.86	6.85
PROB:	0.02	0.86	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.526 MAX_MED: 0.494 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Hydroxyfluorene

CHID: 47540 CASRN: 6344-67-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C20

M4ID: 30007397

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.576	2.04	8
sd:	0.109	0.0711	8.44

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.576	2.04	8	4.25	5.4
sd:	0.109	0.0711	8.44	313000	820000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.64	-11.5	-7.5
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.24	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.523 MAX_MED: 0.642 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Sulfonylbis[2-(prop-2-en-1-yl)phenol]

CHID: 47598 CASRN: 41481-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I05

M4ID: 30006884

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.546	2.01	7.03
sd:	0.183	0.09	11.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.964	2.07	5.95	2.32	6.75
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.54	17.77	21.77
PROB:	0.07	0.81	0.11
RMSE:	0.33	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 0.553 MAX_MED: 0.525 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 0.93

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48505

CHID: 48505 CASRN: NOCAS_48505

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078007

M4ID: 30007122

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.809	1.99	8
sd:	0.104	0.027	4

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.03	2.02	8	2.42	4.61
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.41	-9.73	-5.76
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.33	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.762 MAX_MED: 0.853 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Auramine hydrochloride
 CHID: 20114 CASRN: 2465-27-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J09
 M4ID: 30007240

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.28	1.76	0.621
sd:	0.345	0.403	0.158

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.28	1.76	0.621	3.82	5.16
sd:	0.345	0.403	0.158	895	3010

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	50.15	-15.89	-11.89
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.52	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.922 MAX_MED: 0.947 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Azinphos-methyl

CHID: 20122 CASRN: 86-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B19

M4ID: 30007422

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.876	2.06	2.06
sd:	0.251	0.145	0.685

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.876	2.06	2.06	3.77	5.16
sd:	0.251	0.145	0.685	912	3230

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.17	-47.29	-43.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.09	0.09

MAX_MEAN: 0.659 MAX_MED: 0.706 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bis(2-chloroethyl) ether

CHID: 20168 CASRN: 111-44-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K03

M4ID: 30007222

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.645	1.85	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.271	-2.17	0.3	4.26	6.35
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.51	-13.87	-12.83
PROB:	0	0.63	0.37
RMSE:	0.28	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.523 MAX_MED: 0.56 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Catechol

CHID: 20257 CASRN: 120-80-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M18

M4ID: 30007544

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.56	2.39	0.609
sd:	1.69	1.42	0.393

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.56	2.3	0.691	2.55	4.37
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.59	19.43	23.4
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.47	0.28	0.28

MAX_MEAN: 0.805 MAX_MED: 0.767 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dichlone

CHID: 20425 CASRN: 117-80-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E09

M4ID: 30007360

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.1	2.24	8
sd:	0.875	0.103	15.4

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.1	2.24	8	4.25	7.57
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.23	-15.4	-11.4
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.808 MAX_MED: 0.899 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: FD&C Green No. 3

CHID: 20673 CASRN: 2353-45-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N22

M4ID: 30007131

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.673	1.94	1.44
sd:	0.583	0.61	1.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1	2.15	1.37	2.4	6.65
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.63	8.33	12.24
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.35	0.24	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.569 MAX_MED: 0.454 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Hexylresorcinol

CHID: 20699 CASRN: 136-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A03

M4ID: 30007078

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.6	2.16	3.7
sd:	0.675	0.0862	1.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.6	2.16	3.7	4.3	5.69
sd:	0.675	0.0862	1.28	55200	157000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	51.25	7.6	11.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.7	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 2.02 MAX_MED: 2.16 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 8-Hydroxyquinoline
 CHID: 20730 CASRN: 148-24-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N06
 M4ID: 30007532

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.524	1.73	1.45
sd:	0.556	0.786	2.73

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.975	2.17	1.05	2.42	5
sd:	7.08	5.26	2.87	3.6	171

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	32.66	26.16	30.13
PROB:	0.03	0.85	0.12
RMSE:	0.38	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.484 MAX_MED: 0.414 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20943 CASRN: 99-59-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I11

M4ID: 30007262

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.832	2.08	2.03
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.832	2.08	2.03	3.95	4.64
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.18	-30.01	-26.01
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.26	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.601 MAX_MED: 0.666 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Quercetin

CHID: 21218 CASRN: 117-39-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H15

M4ID: 30007282

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.02	2.3	0.754
sd:	2.29	2.44	0.841

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.02	2.3	0.754	4.09	2.56
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.33	1.05	5.05
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.32	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.554 MAX_MED: 0.472 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Rifampicin

CHID: 21244 CASRN: 13292-46-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P17

M4ID: 30007473

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.47	2.1	0.891
sd:	1.69	0.478	0.277

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.47	2.1	0.891	3.91	4.56
sd:	1.69	0.478	0.277	655	1860

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	95.08	41.75	45.75
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.14	0.4	0.4

MAX_MEAN: 2.29 MAX_MED: 2.18 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sulfasalazine
 CHID: 21256 CASRN: 599-79-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M05
 M4ID: 30007172

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.32	1.84	0.65
sd:	0.536	0.308	0.131

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.32	1.85	0.65	3.89	5.62
sd:	0.533	0.307	0.132	1520	5360

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	83.11	11.78	15.78
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.9	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 1.84 MAX_MED: 1.9 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nonanoic acid
 CHID: 21641 CASRN: 112-05-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M21
 M4ID: 30007156

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.567	1.93	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.251	-1.98	0.3	3.96	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.56	2.92	5.59
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	0.3	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.436 MAX_MED: 0.525 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,2',6,6'-Tetrachlorobisphenol A

CHID: 21770 CASRN: 79-95-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K15

M4ID: 30007210

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.01	2.13	3.64
sd:	1.06	0.1	1.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.01	2.13	3.64	3.69	5.99
sd:	1.06	0.1	1.31	1830	7930

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	82.19	28.11	32.11
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.15	0.34	0.34

MAX_MEAN: 3.24 MAX_MED: 3.31 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 3-Trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol

CHID: 21788 CASRN: 88-30-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091023

M4ID: 30007491

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.73	2.43	0.457
sd:	1.74	1.06	0.208

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.62	2.3	0.494	3.49	7.17
sd:	2.23	1.25	0.207	1510	9090

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	79.78	48.52	52.65
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	0.87	0.47	0.47

MAX_MEAN: 1.67 MAX_MED: 1.6 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethyl hexanoate

CHID: 21980 CASRN: 123-66-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M03

M4ID: 30007174

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.805	2.22	0.3
sd:	1.67	5.49	0.235

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.826	2.29	0.3	4.26	3.82
sd:	1.83	5.8	0.242	617	1210

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.6	-18.48	-14.49
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.571 MAX_MED: 0.517 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Progesterone
 CHID: 22370 CASRN: 57-83-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M06
 M4ID: 30007171

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.962	2.8	0.35
sd:	1.17	2.16	0.286

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.769	2.3	0.388	3.81	5.17
sd:	1.69	3.36	0.34	1160	3960

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.81	-7.9	-3.65
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	0.29	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.478 MAX_MED: 0.598 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Bisphenol B
 CHID: 22442 CASRN: 77-40-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P10
 M4ID: 30007480

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.02 2.24 8
 sd: 1.49 0.0859 6.96

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.02 2.24 8 4.24 3.28
 sd: 1.49 0.0859 6.96 1110 1880

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	58.92	32.32	36.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.78	0.34	0.34

MAX_MEAN: 2.24 MAX_MED: 2.46 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Lactose
 CHID: 23193 CASRN: 63-42-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M01
 M4ID: 30007176

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.643	2.13	0.762
sd:	0.437	0.735	0.547

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.643	2.13	0.762	3.74	5.82
sd:	0.437	0.735	0.547	1910	7740

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.63	-3.5	0.5
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.27	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.443 MAX_MED: 0.43 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Benzo(b)fluoranthene
 CHID: 23907 CASRN: 205-99-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I23
 M4ID: 30006866

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.963	2.24	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.667	1.27	0.3	3.77	5.73
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.11	20.83	24.76
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.4	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.734 MAX_MED: 0.754 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cypermethrin
 CHID: 23998 CASRN: 52315-07-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N09
 M4ID: 30007144

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.577	1.15	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.454	0.23	0.3	2.41	15.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.81	-29.57	-26.15
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	0.32	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.472 MAX_MED: 0.478 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dimethipin

CHID: 24052 CASRN: 55290-64-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K13

M4ID: 30007212

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.1	2.73	0.456
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.696	2.3	0.3	3.63	6.56
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.11	-4.06	0.49
PROB:	0	0.91	0.09
RMSE:	0.32	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.743 MAX_MED: 0.773 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Lactofen

CHID: 24160 CASRN: 77501-63-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I01

M4ID: 30006888

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.687	2.8	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.549	2.3	0.3	3.56	6.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.09	3.95	7.97
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.29	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 0.555 MAX_MED: 0.556 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyrene
 CHID: 24289 CASRN: 129-00-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M23
 M4ID: 30007539

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.508	-0.983	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.49	-1.2	0.3	4.2	3.93
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	50.55	34.43	38.42
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.52	0.36	0.36

MAX_MEAN: 0.623 MAX_MED: 0.641 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5-Amino-2-methylphenol
 CHID: 24489 CASRN: 2835-95-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N10
 M4ID: 30007143

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.51	1.45	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.415	0.77	0.3	4.13	6.44
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.85	-32.31	-28.48
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.25	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.405 MAX_MED: 0.45 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Colchicine

CHID: 24845 CASRN: 64-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J06

M4ID: 30006859

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.575	-0.00123	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.572	-0.0274	0.3	3.85	4.94
sd:	2.07	14	1.46	1730	5450

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	43.7	24.26	28.26
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.45	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.537 MAX_MED: 0.6 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cycloheximide

CHID: 24882 CASRN: 66-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D09

M4ID: 30007384

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.472	1.29	1.16
sd:	0.207	0.599	0.947

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.472	1.29	1.16	3.95	4.88
sd:	0.207	0.599	0.947	1420	4250

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.81	-8.66	-4.66
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.516 MAX_MED: 0.545 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,6-Hexanediamine
 CHID: 24922 CASRN: 124-09-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L20
 M4ID: 30006797

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.561	2.11	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.397	1.12	0.3	3	11.2
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.09	21.09	25.06
PROB:	0.11	0.79	0.11
RMSE:	0.33	0.28	0.28

MAX_MEAN: 0.33 MAX_MED: 0.496 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.89

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Isoproterenol hydrochloride

CHID: 25486 CASRN: 51-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H10

M4ID: 30007287

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.05	1.95	3.14
sd:	0.159	0.0655	1.36

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.26	2	2.86	2.42	7.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.73	-12.73	-8.75
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.42	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.969 MAX_MED: 1.02 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide

CHID: 25595 CASRN: 110-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I15

M4ID: 30006874

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.482	0.0639	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.485	0.0851	0.3	3.56	6.95
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.68	13.45	17.45
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.42	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 0.743 MAX_MED: 0.696 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: N-Phenyl-1,4-benzenediamine

CHID: 25895 CASRN: 101-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I08

M4ID: 30007265

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.719	1.98	1.31
sd:	0.301	0.303	0.62

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.719	1.98	1.31	3.92	4.77
sd:	0.301	0.303	0.621	1200	3540

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.25	-29.48	-25.48
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.25	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.435 MAX_MED: 0.59 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triclocarban
 CHID: 26214 CASRN: 101-20-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L21
 M4ID: 30006796

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.83	0.828	0.3
sd:	1.22	4.91	0.446

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.898	1.05	0.3	2.37	14.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	57.89	31.41	35.36
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.59	0.34	0.34

MAX_MEAN: 0.776 MAX_MED: 0.549 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triglycidyl isocyanurate

CHID: 26262 CASRN: 2451-62-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I06

M4ID: 30006883

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.34	2.19	2.33
sd:	2.02	0.646	3.17

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.34	2.19	2.33	3.48	5.62
sd:	2.02	0.646	3.17	805	3850

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.74	25.47	29.47
PROB:	0.01	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.42	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.815 MAX_MED: 0.947 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol

CHID: 26602 CASRN: 96-76-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C24

M4ID: 30007393

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.67	2.19	5.65
sd:	0.548	0.0432	1.15

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.67	2.19	5.65	4.2	2.99
sd:	0.549	0.0432	1.15	453	721

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	45.32	-1.75	2.25
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.87	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 2.64 MAX_MED: 2.96 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Undecanol

CHID: 26915 CASRN: 112-42-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G15

M4ID: 30006922

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.687	2.07	2.66
sd:	0.624	0.412	3.5

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.618	2.3	0.3	3.62	6.56
sd:	0.271	2.65	0.336	1900	9470

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.09	-4.14	1.2
PROB:	0	0.94	0.06
RMSE:	0.28	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.547 MAX_MED: 0.566 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,3-Diaminotoluene
 CHID: 27494 CASRN: 2687-25-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M10
 M4ID: 30007167

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.522	1.07	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.34	-0.79	0.3	4.04	4.23
sd:	0.267	2.9	0.457	990	2430

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.75	-28.8	-26.64
PROB:	0	0.75	0.25
RMSE:	0.27	0.13	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.36 MAX_MED: 0.402 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Calcium dodecylbenzene sulfonate

CHID: 27891 CASRN: 26264-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G13

M4ID: 30006924

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.05	2.8	0.3
sd:	2.36	6.41	0.297

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.838	2.3	0.3	3.81	5.4
sd:	2.92	10	0.729	1540	5520

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	39.87	28.11	32.14
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.45	0.33	0.33

MAX_MEAN: 0.76 MAX_MED: 0.889 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dodecylphenol
 CHID: 27926 CASRN: 27193-86-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B19
 M4ID: 30007038

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.42	2.17	2.63
sd:	2.71	0.336	1.64

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.6	2.18	2.68	2.43	10.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	78.06	35.04	39.03
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.05	0.52	0.52

MAX_MEAN: 2.3 MAX_MED: 2.41 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dipentyl phthalate
 CHID: 31131 CASRN: 131-18-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N20
 M4ID: 30007518

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.605	1.24	0.3
sd:	2.01	10.4	0.815

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.691	1.58	0.3	2.37	14.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.04	26.07	30.05
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.4	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.458 MAX_MED: 0.643 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Formetanate hydrochloride

CHID: 32405 CASRN: 23422-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I16

M4ID: 30006873

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.449	0.687	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.449	0.685	0.3	3.38	6.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.66	-9.63	-5.63
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.42 MAX_MED: 0.435 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 11

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fenpyroximate (Z,E)

CHID: 32550 CASRN: 111812-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E11

M4ID: 30006974

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.643	2.27	0.59
sd:	0.508	0.959	0.248

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.643	2.27	0.59	3.99	4.67
sd:	0.508	0.959	0.248	930	2590

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.69	-19.3	-15.3
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.23	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.462 MAX_MED: 0.448 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Trifloxystrobin

CHID: 32580 CASRN: 141517-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J24

M4ID: 30006841

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.591	1.31	0.55
sd:	0.607	1.88	0.71

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.17	2.23	0.48	2.55	1.26
sd:	3.28	3.99	0.461	1.11	2.64

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.05	1.71	5.49
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.37	0.22	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.501 MAX_MED: 0.571 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyraclostrobin

CHID: 32638 CASRN: 175013-18-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L24

M4ID: 30006793

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.02	2.27	0.3
sd:	4.77	12.7	0.632

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.02	2.27	0.3	3.44	6.86
sd:	4.77	12.7	0.632	1090	6600

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.86	28.5	32.5
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.47	0.33	0.33

MAX_MEAN: 0.718 MAX_MED: 0.684 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Z-Tetrachlorvinphos

CHID: 32648 CASRN: 22248-79-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N21

M4ID: 30007517

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.771	1.52	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.643	0.911	0.3	4.17	5.61
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	51.38	42.17	46.14
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.53	0.4	0.4

MAX_MEAN: 0.747 MAX_MED: 0.555 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Nonylphenol

CHID: 33836 CASRN: 104-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F10

M4ID: 30006951

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.37	2.05	4.09
sd:	0.36	0.0982	2.31

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.37	2.05	4.09	3.91	4
sd:	0.36	0.0982	2.31	1370	3540

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	40.18	14.86	18.86
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.49	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 1.19 MAX_MED: 1.28 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Tebufenpyrad

CHID: 34223 CASRN: 119168-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G06

M4ID: 30006931

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.544	1.93	1.23
sd:	0.454	0.694	1.16

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.661	2.01	1.44	2.34	18
sd:	2.2	1.52	2.85	0.118	116

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.75	-0.34	3.47
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.28	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.43 MAX_MED: 0.44 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Ethofumesate
 CHID: 34580 CASRN: 26225-79-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K17
 M4ID: 30006824

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.966	2.69	0.3
sd:	2.87	5.8	0.337

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.813	2.3	0.301	3.72	6.17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.95	-3.92	0.18
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	0.34	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.702 MAX_MED: 0.825 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Fluoxastrobin

CHID: 34625 CASRN: 361377-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J05

M4ID: 30007244

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.31	1.34	0.41
sd:	0.267	0.465	0.104

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.31	1.34	0.41	4.17	5.35
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	64.95	-27.64	-23.64
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.64	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.928 MAX_MED: 0.978 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexaconazole
 CHID: 34653 CASRN: 79983-71-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078003
 M4ID: 30007126

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.93	2.31	1.7
sd:	4.57	1.21	2.17

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.58	2.1	3.37	2.35	8.96
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.6	-2.87	1.07
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.44	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 1.12 MAX_MED: 0.929 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Disiquonium chloride

CHID: 35589 CASRN: 68959-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J17

M4ID: 30006848

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.24	2.09	1.33
sd:	0.503	0.252	0.46

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.24	2.09	1.33	3.99	4.97
sd:	0.503	0.252	0.46	1690	5000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.24	-17.2	-13.2
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.38	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.872 MAX_MED: 0.976 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Sodium decyl sulfate
 CHID: 36229 CASRN: 142-87-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H23
 M4ID: 30006890

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.856	2.05	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.775	1.79	0.3	3.44	7.47
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.39	-4.98	-0.99
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.36	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.556 MAX_MED: 0.581 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide

CHID: 37028 CASRN: 57-09-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J13

M4ID: 30007236

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.36	2.06	1.46
sd:	0.441	0.192	0.385

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.36	2.06	1.46	3.87	5.24
sd:	0.44	0.192	0.385	1170	3910

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.95	-24.67	-20.67
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.41	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.94 MAX_MED: 1.05 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Amiodarone hydrochloride

CHID: 37185 CASRN: 19774-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091017

M4ID: 30007497

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.42	2.56	0.448
sd:	1.28	1.4	0.347

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.28	2.3	0.522	3.92	4.75
sd:	2.59	2.35	0.532	1050	3080

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.98	21.29	25.47
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	0.47	0.29	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 0.84 MAX_MED: 0.903 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Potassium perfluorooctanesulfonate

CHID: 37706 CASRN: 2795-39-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E06

M4ID: 30006979

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.04	2.08	2.61
sd:	0.682	0.285	1.93

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.04	2.08	2.61	2.75	17.6
sd:	0.682	0.285	1.93	560	20500

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.19	18.04	22.04
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.39	0.28	0.28

MAX_MEAN: 0.706 MAX_MED: 0.89 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid
 CHID: 37730 CASRN: 31519-22-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L09
 M4ID: 30007192

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.04	1.77	1.69
sd:	0.56	0.0816	0.432

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.55	1.82	1.88	2.34	18
sd:	0.984	0.0931	0.609	0.0101	8.57

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.05	44.68	44.86
PROB:	0	0.52	0.48
RMSE:	2.21	0.42	0.4

MAX_MEAN: 4.27 MAX_MED: 4.19 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5-Chlorosalicylanilide
 CHID: 37749 CASRN: 4638-48-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I21
 M4ID: 30006868

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.602	0.38	0.409
sd:	0.512	2.45	0.509

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.602	0.38	0.409	3.64	7.95
sd:	0.512	2.45	0.509	22800	136000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	45.64	11.65	15.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.47	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.644 MAX_MED: 0.611 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline

CHID: 38700 CASRN: 97-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G09

M4ID: 30007312

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.59	2	1.82
sd:	0.818	0.293	1.22

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.59	2	1.82	4.06	11.4
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	46.03	-0.44	3.56
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.53	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 1.19 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Orange 7

CHID: 38881 CASRN: 633-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091011

M4ID: 30007503

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.19	1.96	1.11
sd:	0.506	0.201	0.251

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.19	1.96	1.11	3.84	5.49
sd:	0.506	0.201	0.251	2100	7430

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	70.95	2.45	6.45
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.77	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 1.59 MAX_MED: 1.56 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Dinocap

CHID: 40352 CASRN: 39300-45-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E22

M4ID: 30006963

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.03	2.38	1.53
sd:	2.16	0.286	0.433

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.53	2.3	1.65	3.37	8.11
sd:	2.02	0.294	0.535	1840	13900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	65.93	21.5	25.86
PROB:	0	0.9	0.1
RMSE:	0.86	0.37	0.37

MAX_MEAN: 2.29 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Octyl gallate

CHID: 40713 CASRN: 1034-01-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K19

M4ID: 30006822

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.77	2.11	0.394
sd:	0.655	0.773	0.14

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.77	2.11	0.394	4.16	5.63
sd:	0.655	0.773	0.14	13300	40400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	63.6	8.08	12.08
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.64	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 1.2 MAX_MED: 1.14 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Morin hydrate

CHID: 40776 CASRN: 654055-01-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C19

M4ID: 30007014

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.22	2.15	2.64
sd:	0.814	0.272	1.71

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.22	2.15	2.64	3.58	5.57
sd:	0.814	0.272	1.71	2220	9860

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.8	-7.23	-3.23
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.35	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.872 MAX_MED: 0.851 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Pyridoxine hydrochloride

CHID: 40792 CASRN: 58-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078009

M4ID: 30007120

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.501	1.58	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.279	-0.792	0.3	4.23	9.31
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.21	-21.62	-18.32
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	0.26	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.497 MAX_MED: 0.523 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone

CHID: 41252 CASRN: 128-95-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N07

M4ID: 30007531

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.25	1.79	0.584
sd:	0.778	0.973	0.296

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.25	1.79	0.584	3.36	7.77
sd:	0.778	0.973	0.296	1230	9060

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	53.03	12.65	16.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.53	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.882 MAX_MED: 1.02 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Monolaurin
 CHID: 41275 CASRN: 142-18-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L23
 M4ID: 30006794

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.494	0.233	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.526	0.536	0.3	4.3	10.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	38.16	19.83	23.87
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.42	0.29	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 0.518 MAX_MED: 0.542 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Violet 12, disodium salt

CHID: 41715 CASRN: 6625-46-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K14

M4ID: 30007211

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.13	1.8	0.838
sd:	0.262	0.275	0.215

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.13	1.8	0.838	3.53	6.19
sd:	0.262	0.275	0.215	776	3870

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.18	-40.6	-36.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.46	0.1	0.1

MAX_MEAN: 0.839 MAX_MED: 0.791 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 1-Dodecyl-2-pyrrolidinone

CHID: 42206 CASRN: 2687-96-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M11

M4ID: 30007166

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.4	1.95	0.781
sd:	0.35	0.279	0.202

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.4	1.95	0.781	4.11	4.69
sd:	0.35	0.279	0.202	1150	3000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	49.32	-12.92	-8.92
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.52	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 1.07 MAX_MED: 1.07 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: C.I. Disperse Orange 37

CHID: 44538 CASRN: 13301-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D23

M4ID: 30006986

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.64	2.01	1.83
sd:	0.323	0.312	1.07

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.908	2.11	1.95	2.36	8.75
sd:	1.17	0.419	1.39	0.236	24.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.75	-17.22	-13.47
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.28	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.568 MAX_MED: 0.657 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: MON-4660

CHID: 44575 CASRN: 71526-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L13

M4ID: 30007188

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.709	2.04	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.691	1.98	0.3	4.2	4.81
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.3	-27.49	-23.49
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.29	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.506 MAX_MED: 0.459 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Acid Red 337

CHID: 44713 CASRN: 67786-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L07

M4ID: 30006810

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.62	1.78	0.7
sd:	0.761	0.639	0.321

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.62	1.78	0.7	3.44	6.83
sd:	0.761	0.639	0.321	944	5650

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	67.55	31.81	35.81
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.69	0.35	0.35

MAX_MEAN: 1.18 MAX_MED: 1.32 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 5HPP-33

CHID: 46970 CASRN: 105624-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N02

M4ID: 30007151

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.588	1.92	2.8
sd:	0.305	0.241	2.86

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.588	1.92	2.8	3.15	8.19
sd:	0.305	0.241	2.86	1480	14200

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.85	18.24	22.24
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.37	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.615 MAX_MED: 0.467 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Darbufelone mesylate

CHID: 47246 CASRN: 139340-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E01

M4ID: 30006984

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.611	2.25	8
sd:	0.639	0.186	6.45

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.611	2.25	8	4.29	2.49
sd:	0.639	0.186	6.45	266	337

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.75	-13.92	-9.92
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.21	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.445 MAX_MED: 0.505 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: CP-607366

CHID: 47280 CASRN: 289716-94-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L01

M4ID: 30007200

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.834	1.75	0.3
sd:	0.964	3.33	0.368

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.976	2.16	0.3	3.6	6.6
sd:	1.53	4.44	0.448	1640	8370

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	33.15	4.06	7.98
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.38	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 0.661 MAX_MED: 0.667 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SR271425

CHID: 47347 CASRN: 155990-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J04

M4ID: 30007245

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.16	2	3.42
sd:	0.179	0.0597	1.69

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.16	2	3.42	4.3	4.29
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.52	-23.09	-19.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.43	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 1.06 MAX_MED: 1.03 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: SAR 150640

CHID: 47389 CASRN: 433212-21-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M17

M4ID: 30007545

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.11	2.02	4.04
sd:	0.442	0.0419	1.52

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.09	2.06	3.81	2.36	12.4
sd:	2.53	0.105	1.37	0.0157	16.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	98.99	21.47	25.05
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	1.44	0.29	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 3.79 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: FR167356

CHID: 48174 CASRN: 174185-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G05

M4ID: 30006932

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.943	2.8	0.328
sd:	3.03	7.1	0.287

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.754	2.3	0.349	3.97	4.66
sd:	1.84	5.5	0.311	1340	3780

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.37	0.52	4.55
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.517 MAX_MED: 0.494 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Lauryl gallate

CHID: 48189 CASRN: 1166-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H01

M4ID: 30007296

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.01	2.11	2.19
sd:	0.404	0.198	1.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.01	2.11	2.19	3.41	7.3
sd:	0.404	0.198	1.01	1570	10400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.65	-18.32	-14.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.747 MAX_MED: 0.714 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanone

CHID: 20359 CASRN: 108-94-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I17

M4ID: 30007256

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.19	-3.19	1.75
sd:	0.0345	21.6	76.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.658	-0.956	7.97	0.301	0.564
sd:	0.416	1.54	278	1.02	0.318

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.78	-11.44	-12.45
PROB:	0	0.38	0.62
RMSE:	0.25	0.16	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.408 MAX_MED: 0.399 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 11; 16

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Nitrofurazone
 CHID: 20944 CASRN: 59-87-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078005
 M4ID: 30007124

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.21	1.97	8
sd:	0.159	0.0121	2.87

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.22	1.99	8	2.4	5.93
sd:	2.64	0.048	1.48	0.0329	9.69

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	106.87	23.33	22.5
PROB:	0	0.4	0.6
RMSE:	1.67	0.3	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 4.13 MAX_MED: 4.11 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 4-Dodecylphenol

CHID: 22508 CASRN: 104-43-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A11

M4ID: 30007070

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.28	1.88	6.37
sd:	0.13	0.0422	1.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.09	1.94	6.19	2.36	9.83
sd:	0.624	0.0199	2.61	0.0114	4.96

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	106.44	20.99	20.82
PROB:	0	0.48	0.52
RMSE:	1.53	0.39	0.37

MAX_MEAN: 3.22 MAX_MED: 3.22 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Diethylaniline
 CHID: 27218 CASRN: 579-66-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091001
 M4ID: 30007513

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.499	2.66	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.617	2.05	8	3.58	0.585
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.01	1.91	1.57
PROB:	0.03	0.44	0.52
RMSE:	0.26	0.21	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.501 MAX_MED: 0.572 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Chlorhexidine diacetate

CHID: 32345 CASRN: 56-95-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J10

M4ID: 30006855

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.72	1.7	4.28
sd:	0.128	0.0181	1.17

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.54	1.75	2.53	2.52	3.28
sd:	1.12	0.0893	0.575	0.194	5.07

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	129.41	7.39	6.92
PROB:	0	0.44	0.56
RMSE:	2.02	0.23	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 3.65 MAX_MED: 3.59 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: 9-Phenanthroline

CHID: 47592 CASRN: 484-17-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L04

M4ID: 30007197

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.33	0.851	5.94
sd:	0.121	0.0602	2.07

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.65	0.879	5.24	2.53	1.69
sd:	0.242	0.0423	1.56	0.135	0.898

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.97	45.94	40.25
PROB:	0	0.05	0.95
RMSE:	2.49	0.49	0.44

MAX_MEAN: 3.73 MAX_MED: 3.58 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Retinol acetate

CHID: 21240 CASRN: 127-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G05

M4ID: 30007316

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.657	2.8	0.3
sd:	0.651	2.91	0.0926

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.784	2.14	2.31	4.14	5.37
sd:	0.763	0.44	2.08	41200	122000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.93	-6.47	-7.73
PROB:	0	0.35	0.65
RMSE:	0.26	0.19	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.538 MAX_MED: 0.602 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2491 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Inactive_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol
 CHID: 21393 CASRN: 112-27-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078017
 M4ID: 30007112

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.095	-3.7	4.8
sd:	0.021	549	2630

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.447	2.1	5.25	2.61	17.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.04	-29.58	-33.36
PROB:	0	0.13	0.87
RMSE:	0.18	0.13	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.409 MAX_MED: 0.421 BMAD: 0.122

COFF: 0.366 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6; 11